

**Third International Scientific – Practical
Conference**

DEDICATED TO THE “SHUSHA YEAR”

ABSTRACT PROCEEDINGS

**“MODERN INFORMATION, MEASUREMENT
AND CONTROL SYSTEMS: PROBLEMS, APPLICATIONS
AND PERSPECTIVES’2022” (MIMCS’2022)**

**November 04-05, 2022
Antalya, Türkiye**

3rd International Scientific-Practical Conference on «MODERN INFORMATION, MEASUREMENT AND CONTROL SYSTEMS: PROBLEMS, APPLICATIONS AND PERSPECTIVES 2022 (MIMCS'2022)» International Scientific-Practical Conference covers wide engineering areas related with technology advances and applications of control systems.

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WORKING LANGUAGES: ENGLISH

TOPICS OF THE CONFERENCE:

I. Development of MIMCS

Computer networks Telecommunication technologies
Methods and tools of information security
Advanced information technologies in measurement and control
Intelligent information systems, sensors, and measurement systems Integrated control systems
Electrical Engineering and measurement
Current problems of assessment and the mutual recognition of measurement results
Modern control methods and tools for metrology
Modern testing, calibration and verification methods

II. MIMCS in Medical-Biological research and education

Modern Information technologies in biology sciences
Modern trends of medical diagnostics and therapeutic systems
Bioinformatics and image processing
Biomedical instrumentations & Control of biological systems
Biosensors, MEMS and Bio-Robotics
Artificial Intelligence in Medicine and Biomedical Engineering
Health monitoring and diagnostics
Biomedical systems modeling and control
Telemedicine and medical informatics Biomedical electronics, micro and nano sensors
AI/ML based approaches for biomedical data processing New implant technology

III. Application of MIMCS

Innovative technologies in the engineering and social science
MIMCS in fuel, chemistry and power engineering complexes
Information technologies in aerospace monitoring
Navigation information systems of vehicles
MIMCS in Earth and Agricultural sciences
MIMCS, nanotechnologies and material sciences
Innovative technologies in food engineering
Modern telemetry and tele control devices and systems
Quality control and diagnostic systems
Industrial and Applied Mathematics for Manufacturing
Sensors, smart sensors and their application in industry
Computational intelligence in control
AI/ML-based approaches for measurement data processing
Mechatronic systems

IV. Modeling and simulations

Mathematical modeling, Simulation in Industry
Robotics Science and Engineering & Intelligent industrial systems, industrial robots
Systems modelling and simulation & Simulation, identification and signal processing
Nonlinear Signal Processing
New methods for measurement data visualization
Signal processing systems design and simulation
Biological signal processing (ECG, EEG, PCG, etc.)
Modeling, simulation, optimization and identification of processes; 3D Modeling

V. Information security of the state, society and individual:

State information security
Information-psychological security
Information security for computer systems and networks
Information security in cloud services
Cryptographic information security & Steganographic information security
Technical methods of information security
Complex information security systems
Protection of personal information
Cyber warfare & Cyberterrorism and cybersecurity Information security audit
Information security control

IV. Control systems, design making and artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence based design
Artificial intelligence based Automation and Control Engineering: (Human-machine interactions, Automatic Control Systems, Distributed Control Systems, Logistics and Supply Chain)
Control algorithms development and implementation
Visual Thinking for Decision Making Adaptive and deep learning systems
Computerized control systems
Big Data, Data Mining, Data analytics Grid, Soft Quantum computing, High Performance Computing
Human-machine systems & Nonlinear control systems

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**MUSTAFA BABANLI, Doctor of Technical sciences, Professor,
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Prof. M.B. Babanli graduated from Kiev Technical University (Ukraine) with distinguished diploma, 1989. He received the PhD degree from The Institute of Physics of Metals, Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kiev, 1992. He received the Doctorate degree in 2008. He served as a researcher in Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, as an associate professor and professor at Azerbaijan Technical University, as a vice-president of Azerbaijan Technical University. He is the president of Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University since 2015. His major field of research is analysis and synthesis of new smart materials, especially engineering of shape memory alloys by using experimental and computer aided approaches. His research breaks away traditional approaches to new material synthesis and selection. The proposed by him fuzzy and big data concept based approaches to new material synthesis allow to alternate hard experimental works. He studied a problem of an optimal alloy selection on the basis of the fuzzy set theory and the Z-number theory. He investigated application of the fuzzy set theory to knowledge mining from big data on material characteristics. He proposed fuzzy and Z-information based models as a basis for computer synthesis of new materials. The research results of Prof. Babanli were published in more than 230 refereed publications including 6 books and 197 papers in journals and patents. Prof. Babanli was the head and the project member of more than 10 international research projects, such as ECONET-1 (2002-2005), STCU-5980 (2013-2015) etc.

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**Prof. LALA RUSTAM BAKIROVA, Doctor of Technical science,
head of department "Instrumentation Engineering", ASOIU, Azerbaijan**

Bakirova Lala Rustam received the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees from Azerbaijan institute of Oil and Chemistry (Baku, Azerbaijan) in 1985 and 1998, respectively. She received the Doctor of Technical Sciences in 2016. Professor and Head of Department Instrumentation Engineering Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University. Azerbaijan EAC under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, expert on technical sciences. She has more than 120 articles, patents and monograph. The field of research includes the physical and technical bases of information and measurement systems, remote measurements and aerospace research, optical engineering. Organizer and member of international conferences and seminars. Co-chairman of International Conference on "MIMCS-2019", "MIMCS-2020" and MIMCS-2022. Founder member of the International Scientific Association of Scientists ALIM. She is head of department "Instrumentation Engineering", Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University.
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**KAMILE PERÇİN AKGÜL, Professor Dr.
Rector of ANTALYA AKEV UNIVERSITESI**

She received her undergraduate degree from ITU Turkish Music State Conservatory, her master's degree from ITU Social Sciences Institute Music Art Department, and her doctorate from Selcuk University Social Sciences Institute Public Relations and Publicity Department in 2006. Kamile Perçin Akgül, who received her Performing Arts Associate Professorship, was appointed as an associate professor at Istanbul Yeni Yüzyıl University, Faculty of Communication, Department of Public Relations and Advertising. She was the Dean of the Faculty of Business Administration of Haliç University, and the Dean of the Faculty of Fine Arts of Gaziantep University, respectively, and was appointed as the rector

of our university in 2019 by our President, Dear Recep Tayyip Erdoğan.

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Eurico Seabra, obtained his PhD in the scientific domain of Machines and Mechanisms in 2005, is Teacher and Investigator in the Department of Mechanical Engineering of the School of Engineering of the University of Minho (PORTUGAL) since 1992. He develops his academic activity teaching curricular units, in the areas of the Industrial Automation and of Mechanical/Mechatronics Design. Relatively to the investigation activity it bases his main activity on the area of the instrumentation and control, projecting hardware and software, and modeling and simulation of discrete and hybrid systems. Another wider area of investigation activity is relative to the mechatronic design of industrial equipment's, above

all in the areas of the mechanical technology and of the biotechnology. In the last years, he has been dedicating matter focuses to the conception, design and development of medical devices and of rehabilitation. In conclusion, as a result of his teaching, research and specialized services, he published about 3 books; 4 chapters of books; 150 publications in international conferences; 30 publications in peer reviewed journals. Auxiliar Professor, Mechanical Engineering Department, Engineering School, University of Minho, April 2005. 800 citations and 13 H-factor

**SERHII YEVSEIEV
Doctor Of Technical Science, Professor NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY "KHARKIV
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Head of Cyber Security Department

Research interests: protection of information resources, post-quantum cryptography, security in socio-cyber-physical systems

Number of articles in national databases – 157

Number of articles in international databases – 157

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Dr. Elmar Yusifli has obtained his PhD in microtechnics & embedded systems at University of Burgundy Franche-Comte in 2017. He is currently Electronics Research & Development Engineer at Myopowers Medical Technologies France. In parallel, he continues his research at Nanomedicine Laboratory of Franche-Comte University. His main research interests are in the embedded systems, embedded programming, micro-electronics and micro-technics. He has already taught Analog & Digital Electronics and Informatics as Tool at the University of Paris X Creteil, at Engineering Ecole of Paris (ECE), at Franche-Comte University

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General Information

1. Location Antalya AKEV University, Kadriye Mah. Celal Bayar Cad. No:5-6, Antalya, Türkiye

PUBLICATION OF THE CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS:

1. Short abstract will be published in the conference proceedings. Selected articles (pages 5-8) will be published in one of the following journals after appropriate research (the accepted article is edited by the author in accordance with the required format of one of the submitted journals):

2. ISSN: 1609-1620, E-ISSN: 2674-5224; UDC: 62 (051) (0.034), DOI SUFFIX: 10.36962/PAHTEI,

Referred & Reviewed Journal, Proceedings of Azerbaijan High Technical Educational Institutions (PAHTEI) Databases: Crossref, Datacite, openaire, ESTER-Estonian E-catalogue. Zotero, Scilit, Researchbib, Worldcat, Dimensions, Europub, Mirabel, Zenodo, Sherpa Romeo. OJS PKP. Website: <https://bsj.fisdd.org/index.php/pahte>

3. PIRETC, Proceedings of The International Research Education & Training Center (PIRETC), Referred & Reviewed Journal, Databases: Crossref, Datacite, openaire, ESTER-Estonian E-catalogue. Zotero, Scilit, Researchbib, Worldcat, Quality Open Access Market, Dimensions, Europub, Mirabel, Agris, Zenodo, Sherpa Romeo. OJS PKP.

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HEYDƏR ƏLİYEV FONDU

OnneksLab

AZEL SYSTEMS

DEVELOPMENT OF A POWER STABILITY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Electrical power quality depends on the system voltage and frequency of the electrical power generation and distribution system. By controlling system voltage and frequency, generated power quality can be controlled. Power generators have their own system to control power quality and electrical values for protection in the existing industry. This article discusses the steps for building an intelligent power generation and distribution control system, which has an electrical protection function and manages power quality to build smart electrical protection. The operator can perform some functions, such as starting and stopping the generator, switching on circuit breakers, and trending for current, voltage, frequency, power, and all alarms on the power control system. One of the other main control is the load-shedding function for Power Generators. Load shedding will be allocated an operator-defined priority in a single user-configurable overall shedding matrix. The shedding matrix may be reprioritized to give greater protection to the production-related drives later in the platform life. The overall philosophy will be only to shed drives supplied at the highest voltage level. Load shedding will occur when one or more of the following conditions exist. Another main control is the load-sharing function for the Power Generation system.

Keywords: Power, Load shedding, Spinning reserve, Load sharing, Current, Voltage, Transformer, AVR, Governor, Frequency, Protection.

ANALYSIS OF THE CONDITION OF METROLOGICAL SUPPORT IN THE FIELD OF NANOTECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

In the modern world, the most important task for the development of the nano industry is the formation of the infrastructure of the nano industry corresponding to its modern level in economically developed countries. One of the indicators of such infrastructure is the level of its metrological support.

This article analyzes the use of a modern instrumental base of high-precision measuring devices in nanotechnology, including the use of metrologically ensured in operation measuring instruments. The modern fundamentals of the technical support of nanometrology are outlined, and special attention is paid to the main metrological operations - verification and calibration. The issues of instability, accuracy, and uncertainty of nano measurements are described. Analysis and monitoring of measurement needs and measurement capabilities for the purpose of metrological support of nanoproducts are very relevant at the present time.

Keywords: nanometrology, accuracy, metrological assurance, traceability, measuring instruments.

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL NEURON NETWORKS AND FUZZY LOGIC IN DIAGNOSTIC AND FORECASTING THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF TRACTION MOTORS

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the application of artificial intelligence in diagnosing and predicting the technical condition of electric motors. Currently, a number of traditional and modern methods are used to perform diagnostic monitoring of electric motors, and research is being conducted in this field. The application of traditional diagnostic monitoring systems in the diagnosis of motors faces problems in determining the normal and threshold values of the diagnostic parameters that cannot be measured in the working condition due to the lack of uncertain information. Various traditional methods are applied to partially overcome these problems and increase the effectiveness of diagnostic control in working conditions.

The development of computer technology and its application in technology paved the way for the creation of more modern diagnostic monitoring systems. Modern diagnostic monitoring methods based on Soft Computing play an important role in optimizing the working condition of motors and increasing their stability. As a result of the research, it was found that the application of artificial neural networks and fuzzy logic-based diagnostic systems, which are pioneers of these methods, together with traditional methods in monitoring the technical condition of motors, will lead to the creation of new hybrid and complex systems.

Keywords: Traction motor, fuzzy logic, neural networks, diagnostic monitoring.

THE IMPORTANCE OF UNCERTAINTY DETERMINATION DURING TECHNOLOGICAL TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENTS

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ABSTRACT

As we know, one of the trends in the development of metrological control activities of enterprises and organizations is the calibration of measuring instruments through the assessment of measurement uncertainty. This process is an important factor to increase the accuracy of measurements, ensure product quality, minimize the amount of waste products and increase the competitiveness of the organization. Such a parameter can be, for example, the standard deviation (mean squared error of the measurement results) or a number that is exactly divisible by it, or the width of the confidence interval. Measurement uncertainty combines several components. Some of these components can be estimated based on the statistical distribution of the results of a series of observations and characterized by their standard deviations. Considering that more than 50% of the measurements performed during technological processes are covered by temperature measurements, then we can say that the errors occurring during temperature measurements directly affect the quality of the product significantly. In the conducted research, the uncertainty in the temperature measurements performed during the technological processes was determined and the importance of determining this uncertainty was analyzed.

Keywords: Metrological assurance, temperature measurements, technological process, statistical distribution, thermodynamics, uncertainty, metrology, accuracy, error, calibration.

ADVANTAGES OF INTRODUCING AN INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Education is a fundamental need of every member society, therefore, every citizen should be concerned the quality of education provided by providers of educational services. But while the results may not always be guaranteed and yet educational institutions can play a decisive role in ensuring the expected quality in education. These problems can be solved by the Integrated Management System in Education (IMS). This is a guide for improving the management of the enterprise, created on the basis of international management experience. What can we get from IMS and why are we introducing it into the education system? IMS integrates management systems based on the requirements of international and national standards. We also consider the algorithm for the implementation and development of the IMS at EI. This process includes three subsequent steps: preliminary, preliminary and main. With ISO certification, we can: improve our education system; enhance the reputation of your school; promote equal opportunities for all students, regardless of their religion, ethnic or cultural background, gender, ability/disability, etc. ISO certifications for the education industry help school systems to navigate a complex and competitive environment, also help customers in the industry by implementing education industry standards.

Keywords: Education, management system, standards digitalization.

ALGORITHMS FOR ESTIMATING THE ERRORS OF THE MEASUREMENT METHOD WITH HYBRID TESTS

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ABSTRACT

During the algorithmic-test measurement method, various forms of hybrid tests were studied, variants of schematic models of their application were given, and their comparative analysis was carried out. The models were studied, the relevant error components were determined and their statistical evaluation was

carried out. Corrective algorithms for error organizers were developed, parameters and existing correlations between them were determined.

Keywords: Algorithm, hybrid test, measurement, model, parameter, correlation relationship, statistical evaluation.

TRANSFORMATION CHARACTERISTICS OF MEASUREMENT SYSTEMS USING A DATA TABLE WITH AN ALGORITHMIC CORRECTION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

The article delves into the topic of algorithmic correction of non-linear transformation characteristics in measurement systems. It analyzes various algorithmic methods that can be applied for automatic correction of such characteristics, which can take on different forms. One of the key methods discussed is the proposed multiplicative method for the correction of tabulated non-linear transformation characteristics in measurement systems. This method is based on the inclusion of measurement results of transformation coefficients, which are determined algorithmically and stored in the memory of a microprocessor. The proposed method is a significant advancement in the field of measurement systems as it increases the accuracy and reliability of the measurement results, which is crucial for various industries such as manufacturing, construction, and the energy sector. Furthermore, the multiplicative method reduces the need for human intervention, which in turn increases safety and reduces the risk of errors. The article also discusses the potential applications of this method and future research directions that can be taken to further improve the correction of non-linear transformation characteristics in measurement systems.

Keywords: The measurement system, measurement channel, transformation function, transformation characteristic, correction, correction factor, multiplicative method.

INTELLIGENT CONTROL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The article is directly devoted to the development of a functional model of the monitoring system with intellectual control capabilities at various stages during the technological process. As the intelligent control system allows to implement operational control and management in accordance with the variation and effects of internal and external factors that affect the technical parameters characterizing the studied process, it allows for the timely elimination of problems that may occur in the quality of the product and the solution of their issues. In order to ensure the high quality of the intellectual control system during the course of the process, to make operative decisions, it should participate as a part of artificial intelligence based on modern techniques and technologies, it should have self-monitoring and correction capabilities during product quality control, and intelligent production as a part of the intellectual industry. should have the opportunity to participate. Industrial devices based on Egyptian techniques and technology, industrial robots, intelligent sensors that enable information acquisition, digital technologies applied in processing and management, software, etc. enables further development of the considered system as an artificial intelligence system. Along with the quality of the product, safety, reliability, environmental protection and qualitative improvement

of management are considered as the results of the resistance of technological processes to side effects.

Keywords: innovative technologies, intelligent system, intelligent control system, artificial intelligence, intelligent sensors.

RESEARCH NEW GENERATION ULTRASOUND TECHNOLOGIES IN BLOOD FLOW MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

Currently, ultrasound machines are widely used in hospitals for the first diagnosis of various pathologies. There is also an ultrasound Doppler method to determine and monitor blood flow. Through this method, it is possible to get information about the general condition of the veins and whether there are any problems during the examination of the veins in the clinic. But, it does not have the ability to continuously monitor the condition of the veins. Continuous monitoring of blood flow rate will facilitate the work of doctors during post-operative monitoring or diagnosis of the patient's condition. At the same time, traditional ultrasound transducers may not be comfortable for post-operative examinations. In this article, a number of difficulties encountered during examinations conducted using a conventional ultrasound machine were investigated. At the same time, as a solution to these difficulties, one of the newest technologies of the modern era, the new generation ultrasound machine “USM patch”, its main features and advantages were discussed. This device, based on the working principle of the Doppler effect, is suitable for continuous monitoring of the absolute speed of blood flow in the arteries of the deep layers. It is lightweight, small in size, and has the potential to increase the accuracy and quality of the examination.

Keywords: Blood Flow Sensor, movement of red blood cells, Doppler effect, ultrasound machine, Doppler ultrasound patch, biodegradable sensor, automatic assessment.

REGISTRATION METHODS OF CARDIAC ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

This article consists of an introduction, material and methods, analysis of heart rate variability, conclusion and a list of references. This paper is devoted to the development of a heart rate monitor model for diagnosing heart rate variability. The obtained estimates of the main parameters of uniform oscillations are the dynamic series. The obtained estimates of the kind of main parameters of uniform oscillations particularly are the for all intents and purposes dynamic series, which really is quite significant. In the methods for recording cardiac activity for all intents and purposes are considered: sphygmography, cardiography, echocardiography and phonocardiography, pulsometry, the processing of the for all intents and purposes signal recording system in a subtle way. With the help of analysis obtains information about the

influence of the heart on the paper of the autonomic nervous system and also about a number of particularly humoral and reflex characteristics, so the obtained estimates of the very main parameters of uniform oscillations basically are the basically dynamic series in a subtle way. Matlab program automate processing of measuring. Finally describes the results of experimental studies and modeling of processes in the Multisim environment. A model of ECG signal processing in the Multisim13 software package was built and the ECG signal was simulated.

Keywords: Sphygmography, pulsometry, signal generation, comparative analysis, registrations, pulsogramm, heart rate.

THE IMPORTANCE OF CHOOSING EFFECTIVE ADVERTISING IN THE PREVENTION AND PREDICTION OF HARMFUL HABITS AND SUICIDAL PROBLEMS IN THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Harmful habits are behaviors that are considered to have a negative impact on many people's health and prevent them from getting the benefit of their opportunities to achieve their goals throughout their life. There is a plethora of data about the most well-known individuals around the world who later died as a consequence of drug addiction. It is essential that those who end their lives by giving up a healthy lifestyle and accepting harmful habits realize the physical differences among health and illness in order to stop young people from taking this path. Obviously, those who elect this path do not read understanding and knowledge articles or watch commercials on suicide issues, but others who wish to assist such victims should be aware of them. The instructional model needs considerable support for young people who are prone to destructive habits and suicidal expressions since the sufferers of bad behaviors are serious patients. It's necessary to remain far from the surroundings wherever these tools area unit used, and if necessary, contact a specialist. It's necessary to not enable these deadly suggests that to destroy human life before the method has concentrated and addiction has begun. These habits not solely damage a human health, however conjointly stop them from achieving their goals and victimization their opportunities.

Keywords: Harmful habits, suicide, prevention, advertising, social networks, anonymous qualified helpers, individual characteristics, psychological services, gender, religion.

INTELLIGENT REMOTE MONITORING SYSTEM FOR SURFACE CONDITION

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ABSTRACT

In the article, a functional and structural model of a remote intelligent control system for surface conditions with the ability to organize research based on measurement methods and tools suitable for different measurement ranges at different levels and ranges has been developed, and this intelligent control system has machine learning, deep learning, expert systems, rapid

processing and expert system based on the direct measurement results and influencing factors for the analysis of the process together with intelligent sensors, the research according to the object surface condition allows to select the level and research method and tool, to obtain accurate information, to make high-speed and operative decisions.

The multi-level intelligent control system allows remote monitoring of the condition of the surface of the object being studied, as well as evaluating its condition and monitoring the dynamics of this condition in time and space, which enables the successful solution of many important practical tasks. The selection of control levels according to different controlled ranges and functional dependencies of a multi-level remote control according to different ranges are presented, and the simulation model, which allows us to evaluate the pollution levels of the research area and monitor it remotely, was carried out in the Matlab environment with the help of Fuzzy Logic Designer. The system allows for flexible and high-speed decision-making based on information obtained from intelligent control.

Keywords: remote sensing, environmental monitoring, remote intelligent control system, oil spills, oil and gas transportation, pollution sources, decision-making, fuzzy logic.

INVESTIGATION OF STABILITY LOSSES OF THE PACKER WITH A GIRDLE-CYLINDRICAL-CONICAL CONSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

In the paper stability losses of the packer with a girdle construction have been investigated by taking into account compactness mechanism. Expanding and constricting cases of conical surface of the packer with a girdle construction have been studied, stability problem of the packer has been solved via numerical estimation by using finite differences method. With this purpose, continuity condition of the deformation has been written for packer construction (cylindrical and conical surface of the packer) and added to stability losses condition. In the first approach the solution has been carried out in boundary and junction nodes of the packer (where cylindrical and conical surfaces combine), however, in the second approach by finite differences method. During packing process stability losses limit has been studied for the first time for a girdle construction.

Keywords: packing, well packing, cylindrical-conical construction packing, mode of deformation, critical pressure in packing.

ISSUES OF TECHNOLOGICAL OPTIMIZATION OF CENTRALIZED COMBUSTION OF ASSOCIATED HYDROCARBON GAS FROM SOURCES WITH DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF METHANE

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ABSTRACT

A method for technological optimization of centralized combustion of associated hydrocarbon gas from sources with different methane concentrations is proposed. A technological scheme for the centralized combustion of hydrocarbon gas from sources with different concentrations of CH₄ has been drawn up. An optimization problem was formulated and solved, the solution of which, under a certain restrictive condition, made it possible to obtain the optimal relationship between the concentration of CH₄ in associated gas and wind speed. As a result of the optimization carried out, the optimal procedure for the functioning of the developed technological scheme for the centralized combustion of the associated gas was recommended. To determine the conditions for achieving the maximum functional efficiency of the proposed technological scheme, an optimization problem was compiled and solved, the solution of which, under a certain restrictive condition, made it possible to obtain the optimal relationship between the concentration of CH₄ in associated gas and wind speed. As a result of the optimization carried out, the optimal procedure for the functioning of the proposed technological scheme for the centralized combustion of associated gas from various sources was developed.

Keywords: Optimization, associated gas, technological scheme, efficiency, atmosphere.

FIBER OPTIC SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

In addition to the benefits, recent developments and cost reductions have sparked interest in fiber optical sensing. In order fiber optic sensors must be made, researchers integrated optoelectronic devices with fiber optic telecommunications' byproducts. In the past few decades, numerous studies using various research methods and fiber optic sensors have been carried out. The most popular sensor types for fiber optics are those based on intensity, phase, and wavelength. An overview of optic sensors and their uses is provided in this paper.

Keywords: Fiber optics, smart systems, interferometry, microbending, and fiber Bragg gratings (FBGs).

DRILLING RIG PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

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ABSTRACT

The main parameters and the order of installation of parts of drilling rigs are calculated based on the specified load capacity. These parts are delivered to the oil drilling site and assembled there. After installation, it should be checked. Since certain mistakes can be made by assemblers during assembly, as well as at the factory. Also, the quality of the material can be affected by the wear of the materials used and weather conditions. The method for checking their bearing capacity is based on the vibration method. The proposed device performs this

task automatically. The unit is subject to vibration. At this time, the drilling rig begins to be exposed to various frequencies, vibrations and noises.

Keywords: intelligent transmitter, diagnostics, drilling rig, automation facilities, Fourier transformation, Information measurement system, microcontroller, seismic receiver, piezoelectric accelerometer, load capacity.

QUALITY CONTROL IN FOOD LABORATORIES ON MICROPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Microplastics are small particles of any kind of plastic, not exceeding 5 mm. Microplastic is one of the main problems today. Because these small particles not only pollute the environment, but also get into living organisms, animals and, worst of all, into the human body as a result of natural circulation in nature. Thereby contribute to the formation of various diseases in the human body. Because of the size of microplastic we do not notice how it enters our body. But they can be detected by laboratory tests. To date, unfortunately, accredited food laboratories quality control passes without detecting microplastic particles. In our opinion, this is the main problem. We consume microplastics in food and water every day without even noticing it. This article describes research carried out in various countries of the world and shows in what products was found microplastics. And also how to find and measure microplastics in the laboratory. This, in turn, may be useful to reduce the amount of microplastics in the human body. In conclusion, we propose to strengthen the development of new reference materials, to develop new standards for microplastics and to implement microplastic detection devices in the quality control system of food laboratories, to report the size of microplastic particles detected in the samples. We also recommend the further development and standardization of analytical methods to assess, analyze, and quantify its presence in food quality control. And quality control by implementing microplastic screening and detection methods in accredited food laboratories.

Keywords: Microplastic, pollution, accreditation, quality control.

OPTIMIZATION OF THE UAV POWER SUPPLY PROCESS WITH THE USE OF A LASER BEAM ON A DISTRIBUTED NETWORK OF GROUND FEED STATIONS AND SOLAR BATTERIES

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the development of a technique for optimizing the transfer of UAV energy using a laser beam. The problem of optimizing the drone power supply process using a laser beam transmitted from a ground-based distributed network of recharge stations, consisting of controlled laser emitters, has been formulated and solved. An optimization

problem has been formulated and solved for the optimal introduction of a group of UAVs at stations of a distributed network without changing their flight altitude, taking into account the presence of different values of the beam attenuation coefficients in the areas of the recharge stations. The condition for achieving the maximum of the proposed indicator of the limiting conditions of feeding is determined for a given limit on the total power of the used boosting lasers. The problem of choosing the flight altitude at which the total energy reaches a minimum at the UAV input is considered. The case is considered when the UAV is powered in parallel and it is necessary to determine the optimal UAV flight altitude, at which energy losses due to the influence of the atmosphere are minimal. The conditions according to which the UAV flight at the height h must be fed at the station, where the efficiency of the recharging network reaches its maximum.

Keywords: UAV, laser, energy transfer, atmosphere, optimization.

MODULATION FOR INFORMATION MEASUREMENT SYSTEM IN THE CONTEXT OF SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT USING NODE-BASED GRAPHICAL EDITOR

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ABSTRACT

In this paper information measurement system (IMS) modulation integrated with a graphical node editor (GNE) is carried out for engineering applications to build software capable of both editing and simulating different scenarios. A modulation characteristic measuring and classification system for classifying a discrete signal that includes a preprocessor, stage measuring system and modulation classifier. Preprocessor detects impulse begins and finishes, determines impulse time, and changes the discrete signal into digital signals. The stage measuring system determines short chip counts, long chip counts, stage jump magnitudes, number of stage states, and polynomial coefficients for stage modulation of the discrete signal. Modulation classifier identifies modulation type on base of measurements using both rules-based and similarity-based classification methods. The lack of educational-oriented software in the IMS field leads to a more challenging learning curve resulting in a drop in student motivation. Software integrated with GNE is purposed to minimize the overwhelming feeling in students in the IMS field by simultaneously providing understandable execution order for the machine. An application consisting of GNE with the addition of custom node architecture and their interaction logic is built to conduct laboratory work using this software. Executed laboratory work result shows that having GNE integrated into the software can significantly impact visual understanding, leading to higher motivation and interest in the subject in students.

Keywords: Node, Graphical Editor, GPIOs, Information measurement system.

A DEVICE WITH A MICROCONTROLLER THAT KEEPS THE TEMPERATURE STABLE DURING THE PRODUCTION OF PLASTIC PIPES

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ABSTRACT

The quality of plastic pipes is negatively affected by many destabilizing factors, which include improper operation of the traction mechanism, vacuum forming, cleanliness of the forming head, dependence on the screw, etc. All these destabilizing factors affect the quality of the product. But an important destabilizing factor among these reasons, of course, is the temperature of the molten raw material and its stability over the entire production cycle. Due to the inaccurate setting of the temperature of the raw material and its change during the production process, the raw material can be more or less liquid or viscous, which directly affects the quality of the pipe. Due to the temperature error, it is difficult to accurately determine the wall thickness of a plastic pipe. When the pipe is stretched to the required thickness, intramolecular deformations of the pipes may occur, which can have a deplorable effect on the operation of the pipes in the future. Therefore, all pipe manufacturers pay special attention to temperature control. The article analyzes the process of thermal stability of raw materials, proposes a scheme for accurately setting and maintaining a stable temperature based on microprocessor technology, and a full-scale verification of the work done. Experiments have shown the correctness of theoretical studies.

Keywords: Proportional-integral-derivative controller, temperature control, control program, automatic control device, heating element, differential, temperature error, deformation, exploitation, melt raw materials, a heating element.

SURFACE TEMPERATURE REDUCTION METHODS BRAKE PAIR FRICTION

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ABSTRACT

One of the promising industries is oil engineering, the main task of which is the creation of drilling equipment of increased reliability and durability. A band- block brake (LKT) is one of the main units of hoisting and transport machines and equipment widely used in the oil, gas, mining industry, construction and transport. LCT, which has a number of advantages, differs sharply from other types of brakes. We have rich oil and gas deposits in the republic, which are located in deep and hard-to-reach places. During braking, all factors and parameter values, depending on their interconnected action on each other, change to a large extent, which further complicates the friction process. It is also known that, depending on the materials used, the design of the brake and the operating conditions, there is a sharp change in the friction parameters, especially in braking devices operating under heavy loads. Considering the complexity of the nature of the braking process, the deep analysis shows that, along with the interrelated action of various factors, depending on the design, materials of friction pairs and operating conditions of a given brake, the main dominant factor may be the temperature factor that occurs on the friction surface during the braking process.

Keywords: Thermal spots, nozzles, friction, retenax material, temperature, brake pairs, cooling, loading, band- block brake, brake pulley friction surface.

MATHEMATICAL MODELLING OF THE PROCESS OF QUALITY CONTROL OF CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

The study's abstract summarizes the findings of years of research in the area of quality management of industrial production and construction production, which were based on mathematical modeling techniques, process, and outcomes of implementing the developed program of monitoring and quality control in the enterprise's production process. The objective of this work is to show to the scientific community the useful outcomes of mathematical modeling in software applications. Quality control and safety represent increasingly important concerns for project managers. Defects or failures in constructed facilities can result in very large costs. Even with minor defects, re-construction may be required and facility operations impaired. Increased costs and delays are the result. In the worst case, failures may cause personal injuries or fatalities. Accidents during the construction process can similarly result in personal injuries and large costs. Indirect costs of insurance, inspection and regulation are increasing rapidly due to these increased direct costs. Good project managers try to ensure that the job is done right the first time and that no major accidents occur on the project. The research focused on describing applicable mathematical models, viewpoints, and practical outcomes of their use in the applied sector to evaluate quality control. This mathematical model was applied by the authors. The outcomes of using this approach are presented in the article. By utilizing mathematical modeling techniques, the authors created an experimental software management and quality assessment system. The authors continue their study in this area to enhance prognostic and diagnostic processes based on mathematical modeling methodologies for diagnostic systems and quality management systems. The independent quality control, which was based on some traditional inspection techniques and used mathematical modeling techniques, revealed a negligible partial discrepancy in the results of the estimation, proving both the efficacy of the product and the suitability of the mathematical modeling concept.

Keywords: Quality control, mathematical modeling, construction quality.

SIMULATION OF POWER LINES WITH SERIAL CHAIN SCHEMES FOR STATE EVALUATION OF PMU DATA

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ABSTRACT

The dispatch control centers received information about the power system mode in the form of telemetry and TV signals. Tele-measurements include information about the mode parameters. Traditionally, the transmission line is presented in the form of a π -scheme, the

results of which have methodological modeling errors. Overhead lines (OHL) may be representation in the form of equations with distributed parameters which makes it possible to obtain the highest accuracy. Equations with distributed parameters contain hyperbolic functions and, in real-time simulation, slow down the performance. The choice of an adequate mathematical model of overhead lines of the corresponding accuracy of synchronized vector measurements in real time when assessing the state is important. The article discusses the models of overhead lines by equations with distributed parameters, π -circuit, equivalent π -circuit and chain π -circuits, depending on the number of links. The results of calculating mode in terms of modeling accuracy are compared using the example of 500 kV overhead line. During the modeling of the modes of OHLs, more accurate PMU measurements are the representation of PTLs by chain circuits with links with a length of 50 km or less, allowing for obtaining an accuracy of the model adequate to PMU measurements. The methodical errors of modeling the EHV PTLs according to the long line equations are investigated. The results obtained are used for monitoring, analysis and operational control of the electric power system. **Keywords:** Overhead line, overhead line equations, simplified models, synchronized vector measurements.

THE COMPUTER MODELS APPLIED TO FLIGHT INFORMATION PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

Describing information processing using mathematical modeling and using numerical methods is currently one of the most effective ways. Some flight parameters are not recorded explicitly by the onboard recorder, so there is a need to develop a methodology for obtaining these parameters from indirect data contained in the flight data. This article presents technique is proposed in order to obtain the required information contained in these data in an implicit form. A method of using the data of the flight recorder, which fixes the parameters of the aircraft movement is presented. An original way of combining computer models and flight data is proposed. The mathematical techniques used in the process of identification are described. The purpose of the work is to present simulation computational experiments and determine all the coefficients at different stages. This results in smoothing of errors. High accuracy is required for predictive calculations. For example, when determining the take-off distance. In this case, an analytical solution is applicable, or, if not available, an exact method based on identification data.

This article presents activities results on aircraft take-off weight and engine thrust determination at the take-off run by onboard self-recorder unit data. Mathematical methods applied at the identification process are described. These methods precision value is given.

Keywords: Flight information, computer modeling, data identification, data smoothing aircraft includes: on-board equipment for collecting flight information; onboard satellite communication system. Flight information recorders act as a data source.

CALCULATING THE UNCERTAINTY OF MULTI-FUNCTIONAL EQUIPMENT AND PREPARATION OF THE UNCERTAINTY BUDGET

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ABSTRACT

Measuring uncertainty is not easy to calculate. Due to the large number of factors and parameters affecting the process during uncertainty assessment of complex objects, it is necessary to perform a correct assessment. In automated processes and automatically controlled systems, the factors affecting the measurement result are different. Engineers have trouble estimating uncertainty. Therefore, it is necessary to disclose an exclusive six-step process to calculate the measurement uncertainty and put together these instructions. Learn how to calculate measurement uncertainty in six easy-to-use steps. Also, what information is needed to calculate the uncertainty, how to obtain the uncertainty capability, and how to use calculations to obtain an overestimation or underestimation of the uncertainty. In addition, you can get some exclusive tips to help you calculate uncertainty like a pro with the help of the extract. Both production equipment and production systems can never be completely described or predicted. It is a contradiction for an engineer to get an accurate measurement and get the process right. Even if the engineer performs the measurement at a very high level, there will still be additional effects on the measurement result and the measurement process. Accordingly, this article can be used to estimate uncertainty.

Keywords: Uncertainty, uncertainty calculation, distribution, budget, standard deviation, A and B type of uncertainty, expanded and combined uncertainty.

IMPLEMENTATION OF METHODS FOR DIGITAL TWIN AND GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Business practices in areas like geographical information systems and environmental scanning are becoming more and more crucial, especially in light of the fierce competition in the technology sector. Organizations are less likely to hunt for information that they can act on right away than they are to experiment without trustworthy information, which results in organizational inattention. On the other hand, many companies are wasting money on initiatives that were either evaluated with insufficient data or that they were unable to absorb. In order to help enterprises design the best strategy for efficient environmental scanning and analysis, this study offers a new method based on environmental turbulence and aerial vehicles. Many businesses find it useful to measure the design of virtual models based on physical entities when creating their own virtual workshop models for scheduling and optimizing workshop production, but a single virtual workshop model cannot capture the interaction of physical and information objects necessary for intelligent manufacturing. To represent the fusion of virtual and real, however, and to therefore maximize the production of the workshop, the workshop for digital twins is an effective strategy. The digital twin system cooperative production unit is used as an example in this study to validate the suggested

approach for building the digital twin workshop, which focuses on the definition and function of digital twin engines in a DT workshop.

Keywords: Environmental scanning, digitalization, digital twin, information technologies.

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE METEOROLOGICAL FACTORS IMPACT ASSESSMENT ON RELAY SCATTERING OF ELECTROMAGNETIC WAVES IN THE ATMOSPHERE

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the problem relevance of solving many methodological issues by means of mathematical modeling is due to the fact that the technological possibilities of controlling remote sensing signals with the necessary accuracy are limited, and considering that the main type of scattering of electromagnetic waves during remote sensing with the help of artificial Earth satellites is Relay scattering and the issue of mathematical modeling of the evaluation of the impact of meteorological factors on this process of electromagnetic waves in the atmosphere was solved. For this purpose, the structure of the mathematical model was selected and its adequacy was checked and For a more detailed investigation of the capabilities of the mathematical model, computational experiments were conducted. In order to verify the adequacy of the mathematical model of the assessment of the influence of meteorological factors on the Rayleigh (molecular) scattering of electromagnetic waves in the atmosphere, the values of the molecular scattering coefficient calculated using the appropriate formula and were reconciled with the data provided in the relevant literature sources. The obtained results show the adequacy of the model. For a more detailed study of the capabilities of the mathematical model, computational experiments were conducted. The obtained results showed that the proposed mathematical model can be successfully used in solving a number of practical problems.

Keywords: Remote sensing, electromagnetic waves, Relay scattering, mathematical modeling, meteorological parameters.

TECHNOLOGICAL MODELLING OF SMART PACKAGING BASED ON INTERNATIONAL PACKAGING STANDARDS

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ABSTRACT

As the end result of the overall process, improperly packaged product and packaging containers with low quality can lead to risks and high damage. One of the current problems is the lack of packaging containers that meet the high requirements for the successful delivery of specific products. A number of internal and external influences and risks occur throughout the whole process, and a brand-new packaging model is needed to minimize and eliminate those factors. Requirements and instructions for the packaging process are completely recorded in ISO international standards. In this article, the technical model of the new intelligent packaging containers is drawn up in AutoCAD (following the requirements of the standards), and an

explanation of each specification is included. The structure of the model, the layers of protection and the used equipment and their functions are shown. Traceability can also be achieved through the application of navigation systems, and thanks to this, it can be determined where the packaging containers are and at what time intervals they will be delivered. The application of the live location system will provide the user with a wide range of opportunities. With drone technology, which is one of the new generation technologies, the delivery process can be carried out over long distances. Application will be used to constantly inform the user and monitor the system. Risk assessment, marketing and financial values should be considered.

Keywords: Packaging, packaging container, delivery process, SMART packaging, international standard (ISO).

SOFTWARE COMPLEX FOR CONTROL OF ELECTROMAGNETIC COMPATIBILITY OF OVERHEAD POWER LINES

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ABSTRACT

When corona wires, partial discharges and corona of insulators and fittings, sparking in the contacts of linear fittings, radio interference occurs. The harmful effects of a person's stay in a strong electric field depend on the field strength E and on the duration of its exposure. Electromagnetic compatibility of technical means (EMC) is the ability of a technical means to function with a given quality in a given electromagnetic environment and not create unacceptable electromagnetic interference to other technical means. Corona discharge on power lines interferes with radio and television reception, as well as acoustic noise. Currently, there is no software for assessing the electromagnetic compatibility of overhead lines. Mathematical modeling of the influence of corona wires of overhead lines, electromagnetic interference, corona discharge, radio interference in wires is considered. Radio interference on overhead lines can occur both due to corona on wires, and due to partial discharges and corona on insulators, breakdown or overlap of defective insulators, corona on linear fittings and spacers of split-phase wires, as well as due to sparking in poor contacts of linear fittings, spacers wires and between insulators. The EMC software was developed to assess the environmental impact of high voltage AC transmission lines. On the example of a 500 kV overhead line results of simulation are represented.

Keywords: Overhead lines, corona losses, acoustic noise, radio interference, electromagnetic compatibility.

THE ANALYSIS OF THE SECURITY AND INFORMATION CAPACITY OF PROTOCOLS WITH MULTIDIMENSIONAL QUANTUM SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The paper analyzes the stability and information capacity of protocols with multidimensional quantum systems based on the improvement of quantum methods of information protection and the development of new protocols for quantum direct secure communication with increased information capacity and resistance to attacks, determining the best protocols according to the criteria of stability and information capacity in groups of similar protocols quantum cryptography. It is shown that the protocols with the highest information capacity are simultaneously the best in terms of stability and information capacity, since the "preparation-measurement" protocols are technically easier to implement than protocols with mixed qudits, and their information capacity when using two bases is much higher than when using bases, then we can draw the following conclusion: the best both in terms of stability and information capacity are the "preparation-measurement" protocols using two mutually unbiased ones. It is indicated that, according to the Tsizar-Kerner criterion, the resistance to a semi-transparent incoherent attack of protocols of the "preparation-measurement" type and protocols with entangled qudits is approximately the same and approximately the same as the resistance of protocols "preparation-measurement" with two bases to the "interception - repeated" attack. sending" qudits (for a given n).

Keywords: Confidentiality of transmitted information, methods of symmetric and asymmetric cryptography, distribution of secret keys, information security, quantum cryptography, security and information capacity, protection of confidential information.

INTELLECTUAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF OIL FIELDS

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this effort is to create new strategies and enhance the control over oil-producing wells and an oilfield as a whole using artificial intelligence techniques. The advancement of knowledge necessitates the implementation of intelligent technologies with the objective of creating a unified scientific and technological oilfield space. Methods for optimizing operation modes for complex technological systems; expert knowledge-based decision-support systems; unified requirements for intelligent system interfaces and modules, as well as means to represent and store knowledge, including distributed knowledge base architectures; and mathematical and software support are among these.

Advanced intelligent technologies and tools built on them may be used to modify goal-attainment procedures. The key characteristics of the applicable artificial intelligence tools that are necessary for implementation at all levels are detailed, along with a suggested three-tiered system of intelligent oil field control that assures optimization of oil output and the operation of equipment. The idea and the suggestions provided in the study can serve as a springboard for more investigation and the construction of actual intelligent wells and intelligent oilfields.

Keywords: intelligent oilfield, oil, production, artificial intelligence.

METAHEURISTIC OPTIMIZED DC MICROGRIDS

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ABSTRACT

This abstract introduces a study on optimizing the control system of a DC microgrid using a metaheuristic approach. The system operates at three levels: first, middle, and higher, all of which contribute significantly to enhancing the overall capability of the system. The first level utilizes droop strategies to achieve an equal distribution of power and current among the converters. However, conventional droop strategies lack the ability to adapt to fast changes, which can be overcome by employing a metaheuristic optimizer. Furthermore, a rise in output current causes a fall in output voltage, leading to a voltage deviation. The developed algorithm addresses this voltage deviation issue caused by the droop strategy. The higher-level controller identifies the microgrid's power output capacity. In DC microgrids powered by photovoltaic (PV) systems, intelligent Maximum Power Point Trackers (MPPT) are presented to receive the maximum power from the PV module. The computed power that the microgrid can transmit is then communicated to the higher-level controller to establish reference voltages.

Keywords: DC microgrid, Droop control, Power sharing, power converters, metaheuristics, MFO.

FIBER OPTICAL SENSORS FOR IOT FACILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Mass development of the latest applications for the famous 19 services of the Internet of things (IOT) becomes dominant a factor in the intellectually-intensive segments of automation of technological systems. IoT is supported by regulatory switching of IoT components and devices to the Internet for information exchange with these facilities in order to control and regulate their functional modes. Our article prescribes the use of fiber optic sensors devices that can be equipped with technological and industrial installations in order to monitor them and detect deviations from operating modes. The development of fiber optic communication and monitoring devices makes IOT systems easily manageable and remotely adjustable.

The integration of devices for reading technological parameters and their further transmission over a fiber optic network gives rise to a number of problems that were analyzed in detail in the article. In this regard, it can be established that the fiber optic IOT has a broad development perspective. This article describes the current capabilities of the Internet of Things, the constituent components of the Internet of Things, and also presents the theoretical premises that underlie the Internet of Things.

Keywords: Internet of things, fiber-optical sensor, fiber network, signal processing, home safety monitoring, technological parameters acquisition.

APPLICATION OF FUZZY AHP-TOPSIS HYBRID METHOD FOR FACILITY LOCATION OF IT SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

Location decisions represent an integral part of the strategic planning process of virtually every organization. There are different attributes that affect the location decisions of companies. Some attributes are so important in selection of location that they control all decision process. We take three attributes into consideration for selection facility location of software systems. These are successful labor climate, proximity to customers, proximity to suppliers and resources. Successful labor climate is an important attribute in location selection. Labor climate is a function of wages rates, training needs, regards to work, labor performance, and union strength. Proximity to customers or locating near customers is important when customers' needs technical support, products are voluminous and shipping rates are high. Proximity to suppliers and resources is an important attribute, because, in many companies, plants supply parts to other facilities or rely on other facilities for management and staff support. These require frequent coordination and communication, which can become more difficult as distance increases. In selection process is very important availability resources and minimal costs. Different facility location attributes are considered in location selection, including investment cost, availability of high-quality labors, shipping, infrastructure, etc. and facility location thus obviously involves multiple criteria. Fuzzy AHP-TOPSIS hybrid technology is used to solve facility location selection problems. The fuzzy AHP is used to grade and set the share of significance of the relative weights for the decision criteria-sets and the fuzzy TOPSIS method is used to determine the final ranking. In the first part of the facility location selection process, we use fuzzy AHP method for determining weights of criteria that are important in selection process. Then by using fuzzy TOPSIS we rank alternatives and select appropriate location for facility.

Keywords: Fuzzy sets, facility location, positive ideal solution, negative ideal solution, fuzzy AHP, fuzzy TOPSIS.

IMPROVEMENT OF INTELLIGENT INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINES

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ABSTRACT

Research investigations of the solutions of an internal combustion engine control problems based on artificial intelligence systems are quite relevant. The power of ship devices and mechanisms is increasing, the requirements for accuracy, reliability, speed and other indicators of the quality of control processes are increasing, increased operational requirements related to economy and efficiency of ship systems and equipment.

Currently, there are a lot of studies which are successfully performed to create the installations with a higher degree of automation – adaptive (intelligent) internal combustion engines, including a class of marine diesel installations. This term means the Engine controlled by adaptive automatic control systems with elements of artificial intelligence that can apprehend

and analyses quite complicated and changeable ambient and take a decision. However, the problematic issues of adapting a piston engine in operating conditions are still under study and theoretical conceptualization.

In this article, a study of the scientific and technical problem of improving the operational qualities of intelligent marine diesel installations is carried out. The problem has a great technical importance and requires scientific substantiation of the directions of both improving the operational qualities and reliability of existing models, and identifying ways to modernize existing structures of marine diesel installations.

Keywords: internal combustion engines, marine diesel, intelligent engine, adaptive systems, adaptive motors, microprocessor controls, controlling algorithm, neural networks.

THE ROLE OF METROLOGICAL SUPPORT IN INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

The transition to new technologies sets a number of new specific tasks determined by the parameters and structure of innovative products to science and technology. Both the technological process of creating innovative products and the measurement of parameters, processing of measurement information, ensuring the credibility and metrological reliability of measurements need metrological support. Functioning of modern measuring instruments is connected not only with the possibility of a purposeful choice of a rational measurement algorithm in a fixed situation, but also with the procedure for making decisions about the nature of further actions. Therefore, fundamental research concerning the design of intelligent measuring instruments is currently being actively conducted in mathematical metrology.

The development of an electronic information and analytical system for measuring equipment will ensure the installation of the optimal range of quantitative target indicators and the formation of metrological measures of priority programs and projects.

The article considers the possibilities of successfully solving the problems of metrological support for the implementation of innovative technologies. The solution of such problems depends on the completeness, validity and feasibility of metrological measures.

The expediency and necessity of the formation and implementation of metrological measures of innovative technologies are shown.

Keywords: Metrology, metrological support, quality, innovative activity, infrastructure, metrological measures, measuring indicators.

INTELLIGENT CONTROL SYSTEMS IN OIL REFINING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The oil refining industry is an industry with high requirements for process control. Nowadays, an important problem is the creation of the concept of control systems for oil companies and

enterprises. Oil is one of the Earth's most important resources. Its extraction and processing have become relevant for mankind. However, in the modern environment, the tasks of extracting oil with the latest equipment, as well as the use of cleaning and processing with minimal losses, have become important. This paper discusses intelligent control systems and their use in the oil refining industry. The purpose of the abstract is to create a structure that will be useful in the respective enterprises. But in order to achieve the goal of the work, it will be necessary to take into account such common problems as the instability of demand; restrictions imposed by the state and many others. That is why the features of each enterprise, which may bring various risks in the future, are considered at the design stage. Also, (it is necessary to indicate that,) the implementation of intelligent control systems in various industries is a time-consuming process. In these situations, the heads of enterprises need to take into account the human factor and help their employees adapt to new systems in every possible way. Among these methods, there are incentives with awards, the introduction of a team to train how to work with intelligent systems, and others. To delve into this topic, it is initially necessary to consider intelligent control systems separately from the oil refining industry.

Keywords: automated control systems, deposits, oil refineries, quality of intelligent systems.

INTELLIGENT PROCESS CONTROL SYSTEM IN AUTOMATION INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Intelligent process control (IPC) has indeed been identified as one of the most promising and essential technological techniques for achieving enterprise digitalization. This study covers key principles for developing IPC in industry and provides a framework for effectively implementing IPC technology. Today, operators in the control rooms of large plants are expected to rely heavily on their own judgement and experience. The present hot point intelligent control technology and means are outlined in conjunction with the forefront of industrial process automation development. As management criteria, technical and economic indicators can serve, for example, increasing productivity, improving product quality, reducing losses, reducing the cost of production, etc. The transition from automation systems in industry to the intelligent process control systems at one time was caused by the intensification of technological processes, the use of high-power units, as well as progress in the development of control systems. An intelligent process control (IPC) system is a set of technical means and algorithms for collecting, processing and presenting information that provides control of an industry, production, enterprise or individual processes based on cybernetics methods and partially using artificial intelligence. The specific use of intelligent control is then explained.

Keywords: Controller, Intelligent Process Control(IPC), System, Software, Programmable Logic Controller (PLC).

IMPACT OF THE TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS OF THE AZS ISO/IEC 17025-2020 STANDARD ON THE RESULTS OF MEASUREMENTS CARRIED OUT IN TESTING AND CALIBRATION LABORATORIES

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ABSTRACT

For the adequacy of calibration/testing laboratories general conditions are defined in the AZS ISO/IEC 17025-2020 [1] standard, and the Azerbaijan Accreditation Center accreditation by (AZAK) audits in accordance with the conditions specified in this standard being carried out. The conditions to be complied with in the AZS ISO/IEC 17025-2020 standard are specified in the sections under the headings of "Management Conditions" and "Technical Conditions". In accreditation audits, the quality management system of laboratories, "Management Conditions"; calibration/testing activities are evaluated according to the requirements specified under "Technical Conditions". To be accredited for calibration/testing services a laboratory that wants to meet the conditions specified in the standard creates/maintains the quality management system (QMS) in line with in this context, it creates the quality management system documentation in which the QMS applications are defined. The laboratory's quality management system policies and quality policy The Quality Handbook, which contains the declaration, is the most important document of this documentation. During the accreditation process, these documents and those defined in these documents. The services/activities provided according to the practices are subject to audits. In this statement, the by giving information about the technical conditions considered, mostly in the technical activities of laboratories an assessment of the observed nonconformities is done.

Keywords: AZS ISO/IEC 17025-2020, calibration and testing laboratories, quality management system, calibration and testing methods, method validation, sampling, metrological traceability.

INTELLIGENT CONTROL SYSTEM FOR SAFE TRAFFIC OF VEHICLES AND OTHER MOVING OBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

Intellectualization of production and processes is one of the applications of information technology and it is always of interest to develop and apply new methods. The creation and use of an intelligent transport system is considered one of the most important tasks in the field of automation. The article review is devoted to the development and operation of an intelligent control system for the safe movement of vehicles and other moving objects.

The basic principles of ensuring road safety are given, the works, standards for the creation and development of transport systems are investigated, the architecture of an intelligent transport system is determined. A simplified top-level logical architecture of an intelligent transport system is presented, which includes task groups, as well as links between them and with external objects. And the physical model includes the functions of the logical architecture, classes, subsystems of processes and placement of places for the implementation of these

functions. Classes include: passengers, centers, vehicles, equipment, and telecommunications facilities. The subsystems of the intelligent transport system and the tasks they cover are listed. An intelligent transport system as an integrator of modes of transport can improve the efficiency and safety of transport systems.

Keywords: Intelligent transport system, security, architecture, standardization, simplified, information, new method.

THE USE OF "SOFT COMPUTING" FOR THE DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The application of soft computing technology for diagnosing the functional state of the cardiovascular system is considered. Soft computing technology uses fuzzy sets, fuzzy logic, fuzzy neural networks, genetic algorithms and evolutionary modeling as tools. Various methods of soft computing technology in solving various problems often complement each other when used in various combinations. This technology is focused on solving control problems with semi-structured control objects. The main informative indicators (indicator variables) characterizing the functional state of the cardiovascular system and obtained on the basis of statistical information are identified. These informative indicators include the tension index, the vegetative rhythm index, the indicator of the adequacy of regulatory processes, the tension index of regulatory systems, and also special indicators that are derivatives of classical statistical indicators: respiratory modulation index, functional arrhythmia index, cardiorespiratory synchrony index, parasympathetic control destabilization index. The quality of the classification of possible diseases is determined by indicators such as sensitivity, specificity, predictive value and diagnostic efficiency.

Keywords: Neural networks, fuzzy inferences, diagnostic conclusion, confidence coefficient.

SEA LEVEL MEASUREMENT USING SATELLITES

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ABSTRACT

Sea level measurement represents a huge interest and importance globally in the world being one of the most discussed and relevant topics through scientific society. It is also related to one of the most important global problems in the modern time as global warming and water level dramatically increasing in the world ocean. However, accurate measurement and analysis of the sea levels can prevent global catastrophe and assist humanity to understand the nature of the planet Earth and how it reacts to global processes flowing in every continent, all over the world. There are two main causes of sea level rise, and both are heat related. Glaciers and ice sheets are large masses of ice that lie on land. As our planet is getting warmer, this ice rapidly melts and flows into the open oceans. The more water in the oceans, the higher the sea level. Secondly, water expands when heated. Thus, warm water takes up more space

in our oceans, raising sea levels. Together, these two things have raised the sea level by about six to nine inches (about fifteen to twenty-two centimeters) from 1900s. This is a big problem for millions of people living in settlements close to the coast. Unfortunately, you can't just drop a long line in the ocean to raise sea levels. Sea level varies from place to place of poisoning. This is due to differences in geography, gravity, temperature, ocean currents and tides. Oceans cover about 70 percent of the globe. So, in order to find out if the sea level is rising all over the planet, you have to restore the rulers in millions of different places.

Keywords: Global warming, sea level measurement, satellites, space observers, planet's surface.

CRYSTAL STRUCTURE AND SURFACE MORPHOLOGY OF CD1-XFEXS SOLID SOLUTION-BASED THIN FILMS

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ABSTRACT

In the current research, the effect of γ -irradiation on the surface morphology, growth properties and crystal structure of Cd_{1-x}FexS ($x = 0.03$) solid solutions was studied. The characteristics of solid solutions exposed to γ -rays at doses of 10 kGy, 50 kGy and 100 kGy were characterized by XRD, SEM, EDX methods. XRD analysis showed that the orientation of crystal planes changes after γ -exposure. It was determined that the peak intensity of the (101) plane increased with the radiation dose and the crystallite size increased.

Keywords: solid solution, semimagnetic semiconductor, SEM, XRD, EDX, γ -radiation.

DETECTION OF HAND MOVEMENTS BY ANALYZING EEG SIGNALS USING CNN

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a method for detecting six specific hand movement events in a 32-component brain EEG signal by using an ensemble of convolutional neural networks (CN) as a multiclass classifier is considered. The paper proposes and empirically evaluates several options for the architecture of convolutional neural networks, as well as an ensemble that combines the proposed options for the architecture of convolutional neural networks, using a blending algorithm and a final classifier based on logistic regression. The advantages of the chosen classification method for the problem being solved are shown. The results obtained make it possible to say that the use of a classifier in the form of an ensemble of several models of convolutional neural networks allows one to effectively identify characteristic features in the initial EEG signals, and at the output of the classifier to obtain the probabilities that the input signal belongs to one of the given classes of hand movements. The use of the blending algorithm makes it possible to obtain optimal classification results by integrating the best estimates of several models, which individually on the entire test set may give a non-optimal result.

Keywords: Hand motions detection, EEG, Convolutional neural network, Deep learning.

EXAMINATION OF THE CONTROL SYSTEM OF AN ARTIFICIAL EYE IMPLANT

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ABSTRACT

Due to various reasons, a person who is missing one eye may experience psychological as well as excruciating suffering. Enucleation and evisceration surgery are the most often used methods to remove a sick or injured eye. The patient is often fitted with a bespoke implant into the orbital tissues after the surgeon removes the eye. In order to keep the socket from looking hollow and depressed, this replaces volume. Once the socket has stabilized, a prosthetic shell—also known as an artificial eye, glass eye, or ocular prosthesis—is placed within. An ocular implant can mechanically replace the lost eye. There have been significant developments in this field. To replace the missing eye, an ocular prosthesis was developed. Physically, the prosthetic seems natural. The eye, however, is stationary or just slightly mobile. development of an independent ocular motor system is the objective of this study in order to give the artificial eye more realistic movement. The detection of natural eye movement is a crucial issue. This study includes an overview of eye movement detecting techniques. Then eye movement detection using the fusion approach is created. The first aspect that is recorded and stored is the eye movement. Then, during the experiment, the sensor array yields the eye movement signal, and the matching rule yields the eye position. The experimental system, fusion technology, and early findings are covered in the majority of this work.

Keywords: Sensor array, fusion, artificial eye, orbital implant, and ocular control.

REMOTE MEASUREMENTS OF WATER SURFACE POLLUTION BY THE METHOD OF LASER LOCATION

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ABSTRACT

As it was shown in the nature investigations, the most area of water in the Azerbaijan shore of Caspian Sea is covered by oil film, the square of which depends on direction of wind.

The research of pollution's of environment by the mean of optical apparatus of remote sounding, mounted on the board of flying apparatus or space satellites is one of intensely developing directions.

The theory of measuring of oil film's thickens by the help of laser location in detail described. The principles of straight--line spreading of electromagnetic waves, reflecting of electromagnetic energy by objects and constant speed of their propagation are laid in the basic of location.

We have developed lidar for controlling of pollutions of water surface, where helium-neon laser “LGI-102” having power 3mW working in the pulse regime is used as beam radiator. During the experiment the laser was mounted on the plain ground on the distance 1-meter from water surface. The prism was placed in the road of propagation of laser beam and used for direction of radiation under the angle 45 on water surface. Integral photo transducer on the base of local mono-and polycrystalline silicon films with linear output was used in the photo detector device.

Photo transducer was made in hybrid form on the base of two crystals: photo sensitive poly-silicon film and unpack operational amplifier 740UD4.

Keywords: Pollution, water surface, oil film, laser location, lidar, photo detector.

PRESSURE SENSORS WITH METROLOGICAL SELF-CONTROL FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

The paper considers the advantages of using smart pressure sensors in systems for measuring and controlling technological objects. Modern intelligent sensors that, in addition to the measurement process, convert the measured signals into typical analog and digital values, perform self-diagnosis of their work, remotely adjust the measurement range, pre-process measurement information, and sometimes a number of fairly simple, typical control and management algorithms. They have interfaces to standard / typical field digital networks, which makes them compatible with almost any modern automation equipment, and allows you to communicate with these tools and receive power from the power supplies of these tools. The technical features of the use of modern intelligent pressure sensors are considered. The functions implemented by intelligent sensors, their structural features and characteristics of the main data transfer protocols used in automation systems where these sensors are used are analyzed. The correction of temperature errors of the pressure sensor, which works according to the scheme of the tensor-resistive bridge, with the use of the capabilities of the LabVIEW software environment, is considered.

Keywords: Smart pressure sensors, data transfer protocols, sensing element, LabVIEW software.

QUALITY ASSURANCE DURING TRANSPORTATION IN RAILWAY VEHICLES

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ABSTRACT

Regional cooperation in rail transport can help participating countries diversify their trade patterns. Improved rail transport can also help attract foreign direct investment, increase participation in global production networks and the scale of related trade in manufactured goods, and diversify exports. Improved rail infrastructure will increase global competitiveness and spur economic development. In addition, improved rail infrastructure will help regional cooperation and integration through improved connectivity between people, goods and services. The operation is carried out by a railway company, providing transport between train stations or freight customer facilities. Power is provided by locomotives which either draw electric power from a railway electrification system or produce their own power, usually by diesel engines or, historically, steam engines. Most tracks are accompanied by a signalling

system. Railways are a safe land transport system when compared to other forms of transport. Railway transport is capable of high levels of passenger and cargo utilisation and energy efficiency, but is often less flexible and more capital-intensive than road transport, when lower traffic levels are considered. Railways are a climate-smart and efficient way to move people and freight.

Keywords: railway, transport, improvement, transportation, transit, passenger, development, delivery, traffic, technology, vehicles.

FMG-BASED INFORMATION MEASUREMENT SYSTEM FOR CONTROLLING A LOWER LIMB PROSTHESIS

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ABSTRACT

Disability is one of the most pressing health and social problems worldwide. Despite significant medical advances, there are situations in which the only and most effective treatment is amputation. Most often people lose their legs as a result of accidents, wars and industrial injuries. A person's mobility is severely limited by the loss of a lower limb, which has a negative impact on both their physical and emotional health. It definitely reduces the quality of his life. In order for a person who has had an amputation to lead a full and active life in the future, it is necessary to have a well-designed prosthesis that can simulate the normal function of the lost limb as much as possible. There are different types of prostheses with different designs and functions, but the most advanced are those with built-in microprocessors. However, even these prostheses have problems integrating movement and adjusting their operation to the individual characteristics of the patient, which makes it necessary to create and improve modern prosthetic control systems. This research proposes the consideration of an information-measuring system based on the reading of muscle activity signals and their further analysis by means of Fourier transform. As a result, the prosthesis may be controlled more precisely and smoothly, normalizing the biomechanical aspects of human gait.

Keywords: Limb prosthesis, amputation, biomedical systems, force myography, signal processing, Fourier transform.

WAYS OF APPLYING THE QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

Achieving institutional quality is one of the main goals of today's enterprise. This requires the development of policies, regulations and practices that cover each institutional element with a single quality view, their translation into written documents, and the implementation of institutional assessments and audits in accordance with the written documents. The study aims

to identify quality and quality management approaches, the development of the ISO 9001 Quality Management Standard and the necessary documentation and document management practices within this framework. Control and evaluation of the system is also carried out through documents, which are the source of corporate information. The results of our research are considered significant in terms of revealing the importance of document management practices in quality management models that are fundamental to modern enterprises. The ISO 9001 Standard is not difficult and contains general requirements. It can be applied in any sector, be it large or small scale. It represents a powerful management system when properly understood and properly applied. The ISO 9001 Standard is completely dedicated to organizations to establish a Quality Management System. What needs to be done is not to create a "standard" Quality Management System, but to create a Quality Management System that meets the requirements of the standard.

Keywords: ISO 9001:2000, quality management system, enterprise, international standards, quality, etc.

INTELLIGENT APPROACH TO LOCAL AND GENERAL PHYSIOTHERAPY DEVICES

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the usage of intelligent approach to a physiotherapy. Physiotherapy as a branch of medicine has existed for a long time, but its methods of application remain about the same as they were a hundred years ago. This causes a number of problems, in particular a sceptical attitude towards physiotherapy itself. The use of traditional techniques in this field has a major influence on its attitude. Even though even traditional methods of treating patients with physiotherapy show good results, people are increasingly turning to medication. However, these methods are not directed at the individual patient, with his or her personal problems, and can be detrimental to the patient, let alone the treatment. Every patient, irrespective of gender, race or age, has his or her own individuality. Physiotherapists now prescribe treatment to patients on the basis of their findings and personal experience. But this is not always the right approach, especially if we're talking about the severely or chronically ill patients.

But we are lucky to live in the era of computer progress, when machines can not only help in determining the correct diagnosis, but also autonomously make decisions about the patient's treatment. With this modern approach to health care, it is even possible to automate certain areas. A global collection of data on patients, with their different illnesses and experiences, will help. By processing this data, we can create knowledge bases, with different patterns, so that the patient's treatment plan will be as appropriate and accurate as possible. This approach is already being used in other areas of medicine, for instance for the recognition of X-ray images. Using fuzzy logic, machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms, data from databases can be used to create predefined patient treatment patterns. This can help in determining the diagnosis and prescribing the right treatment in cases where doctors take a long time to decide on the right approach.

Keywords: Physiotherapy devices, Fuzzy logic, Machine learning, Artificial Intelligence, Data bases, Biofeedback.

USE OF NEW INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE OIL-REFINING INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

The application of new information technologies in the field of automation of oil refining and petrochemistry has not yet been carried out at the proper level. At modern oil refineries, big data technologies are being introduced. Big Data is one of the key areas of digital production and can serve as a tool for integrating technological installations and equipment that have a wide range of information about the technological process and the main production as a whole. The fourth industrial revolution, which is based on the global "internetization" of technological installations and equipment, is closely related to the use of the Internet of things and cloud storage. The transition to Industry 4.0 in the refinery implies the ability of the refinery to integrate digital and physical technologies to improve operation and increase productivity. But, unfortunately, the oil refining industry has a low activity in the implementation of digital technologies. The emergence of new cyber-physical production systems will radically change the traditional logic of oil production.

The work is devoted to the use of information technologies of the oil refining industry in the field of integrated automation of the refinery as a whole, and individual technological processes, including for the production of polypropylene, by leaching, washing and drying, which is part of the refinery, these issues are almost not considered.

Keywords: big data, industry 4.0, security, information technologies.

SYSTEM FOR DETERMINING DIAGNOSTIC PARAMETERS OF ECG SIGNAL

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ABSTRACT

The article illustrates the development of virtual system in LabVIEW software environment for processing and analysis of electrocardiographic signals. In the system, the issues of processing ECG signal with classical methods and also in phase space have been considered, the comparison of these methods have been carried out, characteristic changes of the shapes of ECG phase portraits corresponding to the change of diagnostic signs have been analyzed, and additional diagnostic signs determined on the the base of phase portrait in order to increase the reliability of ECG diagnosis have been interpreted. As a result of the analysis of the sequence of RR intervals using the developed program, a histogram, a scatterogram, a fast Fourier transform, an autoregressive spectrum, a short-term Fourier transform and the corresponding informative parameters characterizing heart rate variability were obtained: the average length and standard deviation of RR intervals, the mean value and standard deviation heart rate, spectral parameters, etc. The results obtained during the processing and analysis of ECG files taken from the MIT BIH databases using the HRV analysis program and the determination of informative parameters implemented in the LabVIEW environment confirm the adequacy of the developed program.

Keywords: ECG signal, phase space, phase portrait, RR intervals, LabVIEW software, heart rate, QRS complexes.

PROGRAM FOR DETERMINING THE INFORMATIVE PARAMETERS OF SURFACE ELECTROMYOGRAPHIC SIGNALS

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes and calculates informative parameters of surface electromyographic signals (sEMS), which can be used to control biotechnical systems, as well as to diagnose the state of the musculoskeletal system. The analysis parameters in the time and frequency-time domains of the signal are considered. A program has been developed for calculating the informative indicators of the signal in the indicated areas. The program is implemented in the LabVIEW environment. To analyze the sEMG signal in the time domain, using the developed program, such indicators as Integral EMG, Average amplitude change, Wavelength, Simple quadratic integral, Absolute value of the 3rd time moment, and others were calculated; and to describe the signal spectrum by methods of time-frequency analysis, the average frequency of the spectrum (mean power frequency-MPF), the median frequency of the spectrum (median Frequency-MF), root mean square (RMS), power density spectrum (PDS), half width - the width of the spectrum at half maximum amplitude (HW). To test the program, files of real sEMG signals were used. The calculated parameters of the sEMG analysis in the time and frequency-time domains make it possible to non-invasively and objectively assess the state of the musculoskeletal system.

Keywords: Surface electromyographic signals, biotechnical systems, time-frequency analysis, LabVIEW software.

BENEFITS OF USING A FID TO MEASURE THE MULTI-COMPONENT GAS MIXTURES

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ABSTRACT

The development of the oil and gas complex is one of the priority areas of the Azerbaijan economy. Oil and gas are among the most competitive Azerbaijan goods and are in high and stable demand from global consumers. Therefore, increased attention is paid to product quality. One of the methods for quality control of petroleum products is gas chromatography. Today it is a widely used physical and chemical research method.

The capabilities of a gas chromatography are mainly determined by the enormous separating power of the chromatographic columns and the characteristics of the detectors. If the chromatographic column is sometimes called the heart of the chromatograph, then the detector can be called the brain of the chromatograph [1,2]. Effective development of an analysis technique, its successful implementation, troubleshooting of a chromatograph, and metrological certification are impossible without the ability to make the right choice of a detector, operate it competently, and correctly interpret the detector signal.

About 50 detectors have been proposed for gas chromatography, but only a few of them are used in practice. The most commonly used are the flame ionization detector and the thermal conductivity detector.

The article shows the advantage of using a flame ionization detector to measure important physical and chemical properties, such as density, caloric content, the ratio of the number of carbon atoms to the number of hydrogen atoms C/H.

Keywords: Chromatography, gas-mixture, density, hydrocarbon, heat of combustion, calorific value, flame ionization detector, number of carbon atoms, sensitivity, quality.

THE STUDY OF LAMINAR AND TURBULENT FLOW IN TURBINE TYPE OF FLOW METERS

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ABSTRACT

The paper studies the operation of a turbine-type flow meter under various operating modes. In the industry, flow measuring devices are widely used on oil and gas platforms and terminals. In the processes of production, processing and transportation of oil and gas, which is a strategic raw material, strict state control of its consumption is carried out precisely by means of consumption measurement. A performance study has been carried out for turbine - type gas flow meters under laminar and turbulent gas flow conditions .. One of the main factors that cause damage to the mechanical parts of turbine and rotor type gas flow meters during operation was the study of flow changes. The proposed method to prevent flow changes was considered. The principle of work of the proposed scheme is based on the connection of a flow regulator before the flow meter being tested to the same gas line. In this case, the transition of the flow from the laminar regime to the turbulent regime is prevented, as well as the rotating mechanical parts are protected from sudden rotation and damage. In ideal rotation, it is assumed that the flow through the turbine meter is uniform, incompressible and steady, and the turbine blade rotates without friction. Under these conditions, the speed of rotation of the impeller is determined by the pitch of the turbine impeller..

Keywords: Turbine-type flow meter, ideal rotation, turbulent flow, laminar flow, Reynolds number.

AN INTELLIGENT TRAFFIC CONTROL SYSTEM FOR BAKU

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ABSTRACT

This article introduces a new traffic control system framework, Mobile Intelligent Traffic Management System (MITCS), designed for Baku for the next generation. According to statistics, every year people lose 154 hours in traffic on average. 1.3 million people die in accidents. The system combines micro-mechanical and electrical technologies embedded system, wireless transmission, image processing, and solar module. The objectives of this study are:

1. Research and design new and multifunctional traffic controller in the box;
2. Design a cost-effective basis contribution to the communication network;
3. Use image processing methods of developing a detector of non-interfering means for control of traffic dynamics;

4. Using artificial intelligence adapt traffic dynamics and update traffic control strategies;
5. Propose a special concept for mobile intelligent traffic control Center. Finally, an experimental system consisting of Virtual Traffic Police (VTP), Status Monitor Agent (SMA) and Traffic Control Integration Module (TCIM). There will be a system highly efficient, self-organized and self-coordinated support motion control mechanism.

Keywords: Transportation, artificial intelligence, information technologies.

A FUZZY CONTROLLER FOR A MOBILE ROBOT WITH OBSTACLE AVOIDANCE

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ABSTRACT

This research paper presents a mobile robot based on the MAMDANI fuzzy inference system. The mobile robot is equipped with three pairs of HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensors to detect the distance between the robot and obstacles. A fuzzy logic controller is built into the STM32F4 microcontroller platform to generate the actuation signal for the DC motor mounted on each robot wheel. To perform obstacle avoidance, a sensor capable of detecting the distance between the robot and the obstacle must be installed so that the controller can calculate and determine the appropriate control signal to send to the robot's actuator. In achieving this goal, the robot can perform movements at a constant speed or at a variable speed. When the distance between the robot and the obstacle is too far, the speed is too fast. Then, as the distance to the obstacle increases, the speed decreases. Such a control mechanism can be implemented with certain control methods installed in the controller. The data obtained from the ultrasonic sensors are expressed as linguistic variables that indicate the speed of movement of each wheel in fuzzy sets. A robot with a fuzzy logic controller based on a rule table is designed to achieve uninterrupted motion with obstacle avoidance capability.

Keywords: STM32F4 microcontroller, Fuzzy logic, Fuzzy inference system, mobile robot, obstacle avoidance.

DYNAMIC EXPERT SYSTEM INFERENCE MECHANISM FOR POLYPROPYLENE PRODUCTION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The oil refining industry is one of the most important industries in our country, a kind of locomotive for economic development. Automation issues in the field of oil refining and petrochemistry are not at the proper level yet. Therefore, the topic can be considered an urgent research problem. This paper is devoted to the development of an inferential mechanism of dynamic expert system for managing the technological processes of polypropylene production by leaching, washing and drying an oil refinery, which can be considered a scientific novelty. At the beginning, an enlarged structure of the created dynamic expert system is given and their contents are revealed. Then the general structure of the inferential mechanism is given.

A special place is allocated to building a knowledge base. The knowledge base consists of products in the form of "if-then". They were divided into two groups: products for emergency situations and products of a technological nature. Specific products are given.

To organize a logical conclusion, the apparatus of the theory of fuzzy sets was used and a mathematical description of the scheme developed by us for making a decision from a situation that arose in production was given.

Keywords: expert system, inferential mechanism.

DESIGN OF CONTROL SYSTEM FOR MANUFACTURING OF PERIODICAL MULTILAYER X-RAY MIRRORS

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ABSTRACT

Periodical multilayer mirrors (PMMs) are coatings used in various industrial and scientific applications for the manipulation of X-Rays. PMMs consist of periodically repeated stacks; every stack comprises nanolayers of several different materials. The number of stacks may vary from 50 to 500. Manufacturing such coatings, consisting of hundreds of nanolayers, needs precise sputtering deposition systems. A deposition system must provide a stable deposition rate and accurate deposition time control. This paper developed a new process control system to satisfy these requirements. Before running the deposition process, the final script is saved automatically to a backup folder; the file name is created automatically and includes the date and time that is why every deposition can be repeated with the same parameters. Multithreading and precise microcontrollers allowed real-time management of the deposition process and increased user interface responsiveness. System architecture and hardware structure schemes for robust PMMs manufacturing were designed. Corresponding operator software having custom script language was developed to provide flexibility and simplicity of operation. The architecture of the software allowed high responsiveness of the user interfaces. The system was tested to verify the reliability of the deposition process and the high quality of PMMs.

Keywords: Process control, vacuum, sputtering, automation, SCADA, user interface.

CLUSTERING WITH PREDICTIVE DIAGNOSTIC PROGRAMS USING BIG DATA TO TRACK CHANGES IN THE STATE OF OBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

You can perform operations to evaluate the state of technical items at the current stage of technological development. This scenario makes it necessary to translate different physical qualities that convey information about the state of the object already at the initial stage of diagnosis. Such a transformation, which is typically referred to as primary, is typically carried

out with the aid of a group of technical tools known as primary converters. To do this, a set of valid reference values for the entire population must be created, and the signals from the object of diagnosis must be compared to these values.

The comparison process may include either reasonably basic operations that establish the value's permissible limits or a series of operations that assess the extent of the values' deviation from the regulated values and establish the nature of the change. Indicators of an object's real state and performance at a certain discrete point in time primarily provide information about how the object operated in the past and do not enable us to predict how the thing will behave in the future.

When the challenge of forecasting changes in the state of an item in future moments of time is solved, the efficacy of diagnostic programs increases dramatically with the same content of control actions. In this instance, the forecasting problem is solved in addition to the diagnostic algorithm, necessitating the development of forecasting techniques that make use of a number of mathematical tools and take into account the properties of the diagnostic item.

Keywords: mathematical apparatus, classifier, Big Data, field tests, recognition system in statistical classification forecasting methods, multifactorial technological processes.

ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT

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ABSTRACT

According to the criteria of prevalence and loss of working capacity, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) occupy one of the leading places. Disorders of the functional state of the gastrointestinal tract, which are accompanied by violations of its motor-evacuation functions, are considered. To identify gastrointestinal motility disorders, it is necessary to conduct studies that are invasive, or are accompanied by radiation exposure and are difficult to analyze. In this regard, simple non-invasive methods of functional diagnostics, such as peripheral electrogastroenterography (EGEG), are of particular importance.

Electrogastroenterography has no contraindications and is well tolerated by all patients. This allows you to examine even extremely severe patients, both before surgery and from the first hours of the postoperative period. Given the simplicity and accessibility of the technique, it is possible to conduct multiple repeated studies to assess the dynamics of indicators in the course of treatment. The data obtained with electrogastroenterography do not contradict and often outstrip the results of X-ray and endoscopic examination, which indicates a higher sensitivity of the method for diagnosing motor disorders of the motor-evacuation functions of the gastrointestinal tract.

Significantly improve the timeliness and quality of diagnosis to expert doctors allows the use of modern computer technology.

Keywords: neural network, gastrointestinal tract, parasites, disease symptoms, diagnostics, electrogastroenterography.

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF TYPE-2 FUZZY LOGIC CONTROLLER FOR A SENSORLESS VECTOR-CONTROLLED BRUSHLESS MOTOR

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ABSTRACT

This study proposes a Type-2 Fuzzy Logic Controller (T2FLC) scheme for a sensorless vector-controlled brushless motor driver. The study also aims to realize a performance comparison of classical PI controllers and T2FLC, which is a soft-computing method, in the control of brushless motor systems where high dynamic characteristics and uncertainty situations are the two main problems. In the study, a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM) is electrically modeled and a sensorless Field Oriented Control (FOC) scheme is applied to it. For closed loop speed control, both T2FLC and PI controllers are designed and their performance are compared to each other. All modeling and simulation study is realized in MATLAB/Simulink environment.

Keywords: Field oriented control, vector control, intelligent control, soft computing, type-2 fuzzy logic control, sliding mode observer, artificial intelligence, brushless motor drive, speed control, position control.

STUDY AND RESEARCH OF QUANTUM INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The report is devoted to an actual topic - quantum systems and the study of their informational components. Focused on students, the report presents the main distinguishing features of quantum systems from classical ones. Considering quantum and chaotic systems, the usefulness of the accumulated experience in studying the behavior of chaotic systems in relation to quantum systems with a wave structure is discussed. The report presents the structure and algorithm for the study of complex systems within the framework of the Open System, which can be useful information for novice researchers. The report presents the results of analytic and numerical experiments, the information content of important calculated parameters, as well as visualization of the results. At the present level of development of scientific research, against the background of a large amount of measurement information, informative visualization of the results of scientific experiments becomes especially relevant. Applying "Visual Thinking" the researcher can significantly speed up the process of analysis, assessment of the state, identification of features and speed up the process of decision-making on the management of the controlled process. Lyapunov exponents and Poincare recurrence are mentioned as informative parameters reflecting the dynamic indicators of development and trends of complex systems. Tsallis entropy, fractal dimensions, stability indices, system memory parameters, etc.

Keywords: Quantum physics, qubit, chaotic system, Lyapunov, Poincare

QUESTIONS OF SELF-CALIBRATION OF SATELLITE TOOLS FOR DETERMINING THE VOLUME OF BURNED ASSOCIATED GAS IN FLARE

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ABSTRACT

The possibility of carrying out mutual calibration of satellite means for determining the volume of associated gas burned in flares was analyzed. Existing satellite methods for estimating the total amount of associated hydrocarbon gas flared, implemented on the basis of MODIS and VIIRS data, are considered. Methods have been developed for intersensor calibration of satellite meters, implemented by introducing an additive calibration correction for the measured temperature of objects outside the plume in the first case, when the MODIS data are calibrated according to the VIIRS readings and for the plume emissivity, in the case when the VIIRS readings are calibrated according to the MODIS readings. The problem of the optimal choice of the temperature of the gas torches, at which the emission of an aerosol such as elemental carbon (BC) can be reduced in comparison with the maximum generation level, is considered and solved. With the full knowledge of the frequency statistics of the appearance of low-temperature flares and the appearance of high-temperature flares, the proposed mathematical model allows us to estimate the maximum formation of a dangerous aerosol to prevent the formation of a hazard and allows us to calculate the remaining quantities if the values of five quantities are known from the set of variables participating in the model. The proposed model makes it possible to determine the maximum emission and its average temperature expectation.

Keywords: Associated gas, calibration, satellite measurements, flame, temperature.

BIOMEDICAL SMART HOME SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Biomedical engineering is a system that includes the design, manufacture and operation of various systems, devices and methods used in the diagnosis and treatment of problems that may occur in human health. In recent years, as in the whole world, some important innovations in this field apply in the research conducted in Azerbaijan. Over the past 30 years, biomedical engineering has been established as an independent field of science and engineering. Currently, biological medicine is not limited to the field of medicine, it has continued to develop as a potential field, making an important contribution to the dentistry, veterinary medicine, rehabilitation, physical education, and sports fields. The types of biomedical devices available in stationary health care institutions are expressed in hundreds, and the number is expressed in thousands. From implant to stethoscope; from complex imaging medical devices such as MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) and X-rays devices to patient beds, many products that could be considered simpler have been designed by engineers. In modern hospitals, sophisticated engineering devices are used by doctors to treat patients. Biomedical smart home system or health-based smart homes are designed for patients who feel the need to

return home after an average time from a hospital or healthcare facility, or who need to receive care at home. The article presents information about innovations in the mentioned field.

Keywords: Bioengineering, biomedical equipment, biomedical sensor, smart home.

THE DEVELOPMENT AND TREND OF URBAN SMART TOURISM

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ABSTRACT

Technological developments, which are closely related to the tourism sector, have led to the concepts of “smart tourism”. The smart city approach is the basis of smart concepts for tourism. For this reason, in order to realize “smart tourism” applications in a tourism destination, it is necessary to develop “smart city” infrastructure for that city first. Therefore, it would be a correct approach to evaluate “smart city” and “smart tourism” applications as integrated with each other, enhancing and enriching the quality of life of the local people in that city, and enriching the experiences of those who temporarily visit that city, supported by advanced internet technologies.

When we look at the current “smart tourism” objects, it is seen that internet-supported applications have been developed in important tourism destinations, which especially regulate the tourist's use of time, make use of transportation services, obtain information about tourist attractions, and facilitate their use. These are the practices that contribute significantly to the quality of the touristic experience of the tourist at the destination. Thus, it is very important to develop applications related to “smart tourism”, primarily in destinations that have worldwide awareness and significant touristic attractions.

Keywords: “Smart city”, “smart tourism”, information technologies, modernization, urban planning.

THE OPTIMAL CONTROL ISSUE OF REACTOR FOR PURIFICATION OF THE PRODUCT FROM MICRO IMPURITIES

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ABSTRACT

In the article, on the basis of the functioning comprehensive study the complex chemical-technological complex for the ethylene production, one of the most important technological apparatuses is singled out, namely, the acetylene hydrogenation reactor in the ethane-ethylene fraction. An analysis of the available approaches to solving the problem of optimal control of the technological complex under study shows that one of the most significant control problems for the complex under consideration is the task of automating the control of the selective purification reactor from microimpurities of acetylene, the choice of operating parameters of which determines the efficiency of obtaining a purified fraction at its outlet. The purity and, consequently, the quality of the resulting commercial product depends on the effective management of this apparatus. The paper develops a physically substantiated statement of the controlling problem this catalytic apparatus operating in fuzzy conditions. The

formulated mathematical statement of the optimal control problem for the purification process from microimpurities is the stabilizing the quality problem of the obtained fraction at the reactor outlet, which is determined by the properties of the process itself and the controlling purpose the entire technological complex.

Keywords: Optimal control, hydrogenation reactor, mathematical model, control problem, technological apparatus.

DETERMINING THE AMOUNT OF OXYGEN IN THE BLOOD BY A NONINVASIVE METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Photoplethysmogram is used in medicine to monitor several diseases in a basic and convenient way. The object of research is a pulse oximeter - a device that measures the concentration of noninvasive hemoglobin in the blood and pulse ratios, based on the recording of a photoplethysmogram from a tool placed on the fingertip. This method is used in anesthesiology, resuscitation departments and operating rooms, is widely used in pulmonology departments, therapy and cardiology. In addition, the pulse oximeter goes beyond medicine and is used successfully in sports, games, professional fields, and so on.

In the ultimate qualification work, existing methods of heart rate determination (pulse), based upon the method of photoplethysmography, which formed the basis for the development, was considered. This non-invasive method, formed on studying the absorption of light passing through the tissue site with pulsating blood, is simple and convenient. It is intended to operate this device, available to a wide range of users, both in monitoring vital signs and early diagnosis of diseases, and in self-monitoring and training.

Keywords: Pulse oximetry, heart rate, non-invasive.

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF MODELING OF SECURITY BASED ON SITUATIONAL CONTROL IN SOCIO-CYBER-PHYSICAL SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The development of socio-cyber-physical systems - the integration of cyberspace technologies with social networks makes it possible to use elements of cyber-physical systems in conjunction with elements of social networks to expand the range of digital services. This approach ensures the development and conglomeration of smart city technologies based on new approaches to building mesh and/or sensor networks. However, all this is associated with an increase in the vulnerability of such solutions to targeted attacks and hacking / unauthorized access to both infrastructure elements and confidential information of users of such services.

One of the promising areas for increasing the level of security is cryptographic systems based on algorithms of traditional cryptography or public key cryptography. However, their use cannot ensure the planning of preventive protection measures. The paper proposes the methodological foundations of situational management, which allows you to simulate threats in advance, taking into account the capabilities and goals of intruders, the capabilities of the security system, which greatly contributes to the formation of not only the elements of the protection system, but also the development of preventive protection measures.

Keywords: Socio Cyber-physical systems, situational control, pseudo physical logic.

DEVELOPMENT OF A METHOD FOR DIGITAL SYNTHESIS OF ELECTRICAL SIGNALS WITH A NORMALIZED HARMONIC COEFFICIENT

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ABSTRACT

The paper proposes a method for digital synthesis of electrical signals with a normalized harmonic coefficient. The developed method is based on a modification of the method for generating a quasi-sinusoidal signal. The essence of the method is to represent the original sinusoidal signal by a piecewise stepwise approximation. In this case, the harmonic coefficient of the synthesized signal is determined by the number of approximation sections. It is substantiated that the more approximation sections, the lower the harmonic coefficient and it asymptotically tends to zero depending on the approximation method. The calculated harmonic coefficient of the synthesized step signal and the relationship between the parameters of such a signal and the parameters of the steps is determined. The resulting ratios allow to calculate the required value of the harmonic coefficient depending on the number of levels of the step signal and with different locations of their switching points in a certain interval. Graphs are constructed based on the obtained dependencies, which confirms the adequacy of the proposed method.

Keywords: harmonic signals, harmonic coefficient, methodical error, non-linear distortions, periodic electrical signals.

THE APPLICATION OF IOT AND AI ON NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING

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ABSTRACT

The integration of artificial intelligence and the internet of things is set to revolutionize the field of non-destructive testing. With the use of IoT-driven AI algorithms, test teams can automate a range of activities that were previously challenging for algorithms to perform. This not only streamlines visual examination and data reporting but also allows for real-time testing through the use of internet-connected sensors. This means that companies can continuously monitor

the performance of their machines and systems and predict when maintenance is needed through the use of predictive maintenance, a new approach that utilizes IoT and maintenance algorithms to predict when machines may fail. With the continuous information provided by IoT sensors, such as the generation of low-frequency ultrasonic waves that can be early signs of machine failure, when operating variables fall outside the safe operating area, IoT systems can automatically alert field technicians, enabling early detection and prevention of potential machine failures. Additionally, the use of IoT and AI in NDT not only improves the efficiency and accuracy of the testing process but also reduces the need for human intervention, which in turn increases safety and reduces the risk of errors.

Keywords: NDT, IoT, Artificial Intelligence, wireless sensor.

DEVELOPMENT OF THERMAL UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLE (UAV) SYSTEM FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN BUILDINGS

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ABSTRACT

In the scope of this study, a system was developed for performing essential thermal measurements with the aim of support energy efficiency in industrial places and public dwellings and determining heat energy losses. The system was established through using unmanned aerial vehicle, thermal cameras with wireless and RGB communication. Primarily calibration tests were carried out for flight time of unmanned aerial vehicle, landing after the flight, accuracy of lift-off, balance tests, images taken from colored and thermal camera. Radiometric, thermal and geometric calibrations were fulfilled at the calibration stage. After the calibration stage, thermal measurements were performed and heat losses were determined. It was selected two buildings and a parking lot, then essential measurements were done. According to heat loss calculation published by Turkish Plumbing and Engineers Association, heat losses were calculated, heat loss values taken from thermal camera were compared and verifications and optimization processes were carried out for the system.

Keywords: Colored camera, energy efficiency, heat losses, thermal camera, unmanned aerial vehicle.

DETECTION OF ADVANCED PERSISTENT THREATS USING SIEM RULESETS

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ABSTRACT

Cyber-attacks move towards a sophisticated, destructive, and persistent position, as in the case of Stuxnet, Dark Hotel, Poseidon, and Carbanak. These attacks are called Advanced Persistent Threats (APT) in which an intruder establishes an undetected presence in a network in order to steal sensitive data over a prolonged period of time. In today's digitalized life, these attacks threaten the main critical life areas. This threat is followed by critical infrastructures, finance, energy, and aviation agencies. One of the biggest APT attacks was Stuxnet which targeted software on computers controlling the programmable logic controllers (PLCs) used to

automate machine processes. The other one was the Deep Panda attack discovered in 2015 which compromised over 4 million US personnel records because of the ongoing cyberwar between China and the U.S. This paper attempts to explain the difficulties of detecting APTs and to examine the studies in this area. In addition, this paper presents a new approach to detecting APTs using the SIEM solution. In this approach, it is recommended to establish APT rulesets in SIEM solutions by using the indicators left behind by the attacks. In the rulesets, 3 basic indicator types are considered, and examples are shared.

Keywords: Cyber security, cyber war, APT, SIEM, Intrusion Detection System.

THE PARADIGM OF BUILDING SECURE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR DETECTING DEEP FAKE MODIFICATIONS OF BIOMETRIC IMAGES BASED ON NEURAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Digital transformation of industrial processes at critical infrastructure objects in the space of Industry 4.0 and cyber security of digitalization processes, in particular under the program "EU4Digital: Cyber Security - East", which reflects the vector of development of systems for protecting objects with digital content, are united by the tasks of the "intellectualization" structure – cyber security" aimed at countering deepfake.

The work proposes a paradigm of safe information technologies (IT) for detecting deepfake modifications of a biometric image based on convolutional neural networks, which is developed by: a concept based on a deepfake detection system and a decision support system; the methodology of creating neural network IT as a constructive algorithm for the functioning of information resources (IR) in the information system (IS) based on information processes (IP) and information networks (IN) and elements of security management (M); comprehensive security system (CSS) of neural network IT at the level of "deepfake modification – detection". A multi-level complex security system is deployed with security belts and security technologies per IT components and subsystems of information protection at the detection, blocking, and neutralization of in incidental and intentional threats.

An algorithm for the detection of deepfake modifications of biometric images has been developed: splitting the video file of the biometric image into frames – detection – reproduction of normalized images of faces – processing through a neural network – calculation of the feature matrix – construction of an image classifier. The created paradigm is transformed into various subject areas of intellectualization of infrastructure objects to ensure appropriate security profiles.

Keywords: Intellectualization, cyber security, biometric image, deepfake, information technology, neural networks, paradigm, detection system, algorithm, comprehensive security system.

MODIFIED FOURIER TRANSFORM FOR IMPROVING SPECTRAL ANALYSIS OF RADIO SIGNALS

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ABSTRACT

The paper proposes an improved method of spectral analysis of radio signals of signals, the improvement was achieved due to the use of a modified Fourier transform in the transformation of signals. This makes it possible to distinguish the signal very precisely and to determine its characteristics against the background of many obstacles in the air space. The obtained results fully confirm the advantages of the proposed method. The simulation results proved the advantage of the modified Fourier method of radio signal analysis of signals, the advantage was achieved due to its use in signal transformation. The proposed method increases the accuracy of detecting signals of means of covert information acquisition by 14%.

Keywords: spectrum, radio monitoring, means of secretly obtaining information, Fourier transformation.

METHODOLOGY FOR PLANNING THE LOCATION OF SWITCHING NODES OF IP- TELEPHONY NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of the topic is due to the high pace of development and implementation of new systems and processes in information structures and the lack of a methodology for determining the effectiveness of using new infocommunication technologies in them. Currently, there are no unified scientifically based methods for assessing the feasibility and effectiveness of using IP telephony technology. This is due to insufficient experience in the operation of telecommunication systems based on IP telephony technology and their significant difference from traditional telephone systems. It is indicated that for optimal planning of the location of switching nodes of IP-telephony networks, a methodology has been developed, consisting of the development of a mathematical basis for constructing the projected IP-telephony network, algorithmic implementation and estimation of the complexity of the implementation of this algorithm, which can be used in the design of real IP-telephony networks. The algorithmic implementation of the developed technique uses three arrays from among the nodes of the network, i.e. the first array contains labels with two values, the second array contains the distances - the current shortest distances from the specified vertex to the corresponding vertex, and the third array contains the vertex numbers. In turn, the algorithmic implementation depends on how the source vertex is found, how the set of unmarked vertices is stored, and how labels are updated.

Keywords: Telecommunications network, IP-telephony technology, packet switching of flows, planning of the location of switching nodes, algorithmic implementation of the planning methodology, subscriber network, parameters of information systems, network parameters.

PROSPECTS FOR THE USE OF ACTIVE ASPIRATION ALARM SYSTEMS IN FIRE SAFETY SYSTEMS OF MANY-STOURED HIGH BUILDINGS

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ABSTRACT

At present, multi-story high-rise buildings are becoming one of the most widely used buildings in cities. Now it is very difficult to imagine urban architecture without them. The increase in the urban population in cities is the result of an increase in the level of urbanization. As a result, the price of land increases due to the lack of free land in cities. Thus, the construction of multi-story buildings has become an inevitable solution to this issue, but this, in turn, has led to new problems.

Depending on the purpose, composition, and number of technical systems, multi-story buildings are complex engineering and technical objects. On the one hand, the use of engineering and technical systems leads to an increase in the standard of living of people living standards, but they are also the main causes of new problems. For example, high-rise buildings are quite large consumers of electrical energy, both as objects and as subjects of these buildings, and this, in turn, leads to an increase in the likelihood of a fire in them.

To prevent such undesirable cases, one has to use fire safety systems, one of the components of building automation. One of the main responsibilities of fire safety systems is to determine the initial stage of ignition and quickly detect its source, only, in this case, it can be eliminated or at least localized. The life and property of people can be protected.

The main purpose of this article is to consider the currently unused active aspiration system in multi-story high-rise buildings as an alternative to currently used systems to improve efficiency in terms of fire safety. The article includes the appointment of an active aspiration system, the principle of operation, and the main characteristics, and functions of those designed for early fire detection. In addition, several options and a comparative analysis of an active aspiration system are considered to create a highly efficient fire safety system for high-rise buildings.

Keywords: fire protection systems, smoke exhaust systems, fire protection sensors, aspirator alarm systems, automatic building systems.

THE GROWING IMPORTANCE AND RELEVANCE OF GAS FILTERS IN THE MODERN GAS INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Natural gas is a mixture of various hydrocarbon gases. It can be found both alone and mixed with crude oil in oil fields, it is considered the most widely used fuel in industry, it is used in a wide range of industries such as glass, plastic, fertilizer, and steel. In addition, natural gas is the main fuel for household heating systems almost all over the world. Because it burns more ecologically, is safer and does not pollute the environment, it is substantially ahead of other fuels (such as coal and diesel) worldwide. However, we must note that natural gas can contain

many liquid and solid contaminants. In order for the processes to be effective in the whole process, it must be cleaned effectively starting from the initial stage.

Keywords: Natural gas, gas filters, natural gas contamination.

AN ARCHITECTURE FOR TANGLE-BASED MEDICAL DATA TRANSMISSION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Electronic health information exchange allows providers to healthcare providers and patients to securely access vital medical information of the patient and share it in electronically with other healthcare providers. However, existing health systems for the exchange of medical data faced with a number of problems, in particular: security, confidentiality and fragmentation of medical data. Data information systems are isolated because each medical institution, laboratory, doctor use their own system. The patient cannot access their medical information in the right time, since patients still do not have access to these systems. And the exchange of medical information between doctors occurs through mail or patients carry their own medical records with them admission to reception. In healthcare, there is no single system that allows both doctors and patients to have permanent access to the history the patient's illness and prescribed treatment. The paper considers the electronic health system eHealth. In this system, all medical data is stored on central component, and physicians using information systems gets access to them. However, this system has its limitations: single point of failure, lack of a unified medical information systems and patients still do not have access to their medical data. Therefore, one of the solutions to these problems is to create systems for exchanging medical information using directed acyclic graph (DAG). DAG will allow freely exchange data with a guarantee of their integrity. The patient's medical records will be stored in a distributed ledger, and not on the server of the medical institution. So no one can change patient data or deny him access to his own data. The use of DAG is considered on the example of the transfer of medical patient data to the doctor. The process of creating and sending medical data to DAG is illustrated with a specific example.

Keywords: directed acyclic graph, electronic healthcare system, healthcare data exchange, medical patient data.

MODERN METHODS OF STUDYING INACCESSIBLE MOUNTAIN RELIEF WITH GIS TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The application of these methods, in addition to remote means of studying the Earth's surface, makes it possible to carry out complex studies of the modern condition of mountain ranges and mountain villages.

The development of such a system is complicated by different levels of accessibility information for each key site, so creating a project GIS that concentrates data on a single cartographic basis with an appropriate database for subsequent automated analysis of this information is the most effective way to address assigned tasks.

On-based SRTM DEM using GIS technology performed morphometric analysis of relief Shinchay-Damiraparanchay mudflow basins. With these purpose-built maps of hypsometry, slopes, aspect, range relief and drainage density, indexes, dissection and ruggedness, and surface curvature. Also analyzed the areal distribution of these parameters by grade.

Now, in connection with the development of digital technologies and the broad availability of data of remote sensing, detailed assessment of relief became possible. Application of the digital models of a relief (DMR) considerably simplified the morphometric analysis of a relief.

Keywords: GIS, DEM, morphometric analysis, range relief, SRTM.

OPTIMIZATION OF BEVEL GEAR PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

Design problems, and especially the improvement of drives, take one of the most important place in modern mechanical engineering. An various drives are now very widespread, it includes mechanical reducers very often. This work examines in detail the issue of optimization of bevel gears, which are used when it is necessary to transmit motion at a certain angle (usually 90°). Modern trends in the development of various drives are primarily focused on reducing their mass and dimensions. As the dimensions of the transmission decrease, the dimensions of other parts and components also decrease, and accordingly, their cost. To solve the problem, the modern parametric design system "Autodesk Inventor Professional 2020" is used in this work. The purpose of the work is to determine the optimal (rational) parameters of the bevel gear, from the point of view of reducing its mass and dimensions. That is, it is necessary to obtain the dependence of the mass of the transmission (gear wheels) on its gear ratios. To obtain dependencies, it is necessary to choose the most common types of bevel gears, so it is also important to perform a brief analysis of bevel gears types. As a result of the study, it was found that gear ratios of 4 or more are the most optimal for gears with round teeth, and for spur bevel gears, gear ratios from 3.15 to 5 are the most optimal.

Keywords: drive, mechanical reducer, bevel gear, optimization, gear ratio.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF A MULTI-COPTER WITH A HYBRID POWER SYSTEM AT THE TAKEOFF

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses a model of a multicopter with a hybrid power system as an alternative to installations with energy sources exclusively based on electrochemical batteries as the main onboard power source. When using batteries, the flight time is usually limited to 10-20 minutes. The main results of the preliminary analysis and modeling of the working processes of the subsystems of the hybrid power system are presented. Subsystems include an internal combustion engine, a permanent magnet alternator and voltage rectification module, electric motors with propellers, and control systems. The model of a sequential hybrid power system is analyzed at the stage of takeoff of a multicopter. To simulate the electrical machines of a hybrid power system, analytical and numerical calculation methods were used, which made it possible to determine the inductance and phase flux linkage for the generator and electric motors of the multicopter. The developed multicopter dynamics model with restrictions on many parameters made it possible to evaluate the take-off process to a given height of 10 m. The model showed a decrease in the frequency of rotation of the generator drive motor and a decrease in the supply voltage of on-board consumers. From the simulation results of the presented electrical architecture, it becomes necessary to add a battery to its power branch. The main task of the battery is to stabilize the voltage of onboard consumers in case of a sharp change in the energy balance of power, as well as to perform an emergency landing.

Keywords: Multicopter, hybrid power system, internal combustion engine, generator, control system, modeling, onboard voltage regulation.

PROBABILISTIC-PHYSICAL MODEL OF GAN:SI RADIATION RECOMBINATION SPECTRA LONG-TERM EVOLUTION DUE TO MICROWAVE RADIATION, WEAK MAGNETIC FIELD, AND ELECTRON RADIATION TREATMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The influence of microwave radiation (MR) (2.45 GHz), weak magnetic field (WMF) (60 mT) and electron radiation (ER) (4 MeV) treatments on processes of defects reorganization in near-surface layers of GaN:Si have been studied. Long-term processes of photoluminescence spectra transformations after MR, WMF and ER treatments have been modeled. Our approximation is based on the assumption that evolution processes in the defect subsystem of a crystal are random events, and distribution of the random value – the time before a random event – is a subject to the Weibull-Gnedenko law. Qualitative and quantitative agreements between experimental data and theoretical models of long-term observed changes caused by noted treatments have been obtained. According to proposed approach, the same mechanism could be applied for explanation long-term reorganizations after noted treatments semiconductor material. Moreover, this approach enables to explain non-monotonous behavior of photoluminescence spectra after MF, WMF and ER treatments and could be applied to prediction the consequences of noted actions

Keywords: Microwave radiation, weak magnetic field, electron radiation, photoluminescence, gallium nitride.

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE OPERATION OF AUDIO FREQUENCY (NO JUNCTION) AND JUNCTION RAIL CIRCUITS

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ABSTRACT

Rail circuits are the basic elements of modern railway automation and telemechanics systems, performing the functions of track sensors and telemechanical channels. It is shown that the calculation of their operating boundary conditions becomes more complicated with the application of junctionless audio frequency rail circuits. The analysis of track circuits consists of studying the changes in their operation in various modes when the circuit parameters are changed. During the analysis, the optimal values of the parameters of the circuit elements and the frequency of the power source are determined for the given operating conditions. An analysis of the factors affecting the operating currents and voltages of such rail circuit schemes has been carried out. When analyzing and calculating a track circuit, it is assumed that the track line and equipment elements are linear, that is, their parameters do not depend on the flowing currents. To simplify the calculations, the track circuit is represented by the corresponding mathematical model (equivalent circuit) for each mode. Depending on the type of equivalent circuit used, four-pole and multi-pole models are distinguished. At the same time, the analysis and reporting of jointed rail circuits are carried out. Based on their results, the directions that allow for more accurate modeling of the operating modes of the circuits of the non-joint audio frequency rail circuits have been determined.

Keywords: Rail circuits, train traffic safety, audio frequency (no junction) track circuits, junction rail circuits, signaling system, track sensors, mathematical model, remote conditioning monitoring.

THE METHOD OF LOCALIZATION OF SIGNALS OF RADIO TRANSMITTING DEVICES

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ABSTRACT

The set of acoustic intelligence tools used for the unauthorized recording of speech information is quite large. Therefore, the task of detection, recognition, and localization of radio devices that are illegally operating within the radius of radio monitoring is a very difficult task. This report is devoted to the localization of radio signals, specifically to the development of a mathematical model of the accuracy of the allocation of signals of radio devices based on the long-range method and gradient analysis. The concept of the geometric coefficient is used to estimate the amount of reduction in the accuracy of the error determination relative to the accuracy of the geometric parameter determination. The concept of the geometric factor is used to estimate the amount of reduction in the accuracy of the error determination relative to the accuracy of the determination of the geometric parameter. Gradient analysis methods were

used to form the error localization model. mathematical modeling was carried out. The practical results of the modeling allow you to simulate the probability of detecting errors for a typical house, and with the help of a minimum number of direction finder antennas, you can detect the signals of illegal radio devices with an accuracy of up to 0.5 m of the volume parameter.

Keywords: random signal, localization, detection probability, mathematical expectations.

THE FEATURES AND PROSPECTS OF CLINICAL PHARMACY SERVICES OPPORTUNITIES WITH STATEMENT ON PHARMACEUTICAL CARE IN WESTERN GEORGIA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the opportunities and challenges of clinical pharmacy services from the perspective of practitioners in various clinics and hospitals in western Georgia. This improves the quality of life for patients. Thus, pharmaceutical care can be considered as a form of clinical pharmacy. It can be considered the establishment of clinical pharmacy in Georgia, when the record of clinical pharmacy appeared in the National Register of Qualifications, however, there is still no legal framework. a document that would define the role of clinical pharmacy and career opportunities, although many clinics participate in international clinical trials, in which, according to the international protocol, a clinical pharmacist should participate, although at this stage such a profession and personnel are not fixed in clinics, it turns out that general pharmacists practitioners formally perform the functions of a clinical pharmacist, which is confirmed by our survey. The role of the pharmacist in Georgia needs to be expanded, which is still a problem: Some clinical guidelines have been prepared in Georgia. Unfortunately, we have not yet noticed a pharmacist in the writing group of any of the guidelines. We believe that the participation of the clinical pharmacist in the process of preparing recommendations is already necessary. Our study was conducted on the basis of the Medical Center of Western Georgia - "Evex Hospitals". Western Georgia Referral Hospital is the largest hospital in the Evexi Hospitals network, serving more than 1,200 inpatients and 10,000 outpatients every month and performing up to 600 surgical interventions. The hospital has an emergency room for both adults and children. In the entire region, only the referral hospital of Western Georgia has a department of neonatology and pediatric resuscitation. The hospital has a full-fledged cardiology and cardiac surgery service, which contributes to reducing mortality from cardiovascular insufficiency throughout the region. We have established that clinical pharmacy services are actually implemented in the EVEX network hospitals in Western Georgia, although there is still no specific legal framework. Clinic Networked health workers are receptive to clinical pharmacy services, but we have identified some potential challenges to strengthening and promoting clinical pharmacy services. In addition, existing opportunities to improve services should be used wisely. The participation of a clinical pharmacist is important at all stages of creating a treatment algorithm.

Keywords: Pharmaceutical services, professional practice, pharmacy service, hospital, pharmacists, medical staff, quality, Georgia.

DEVELOPMENT, INSTRUMENTATION, AND ANALYSIS OF RECOIL THROUGH A RIFLESCOPE

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ABSTRACT

The research and development of new technologies to incorporate in the sport optics field have orientated the design, development, and construction of new riflescopes with state-of-the-art materials, processes, and technology. With each evolution, the riflescope should be evaluated to observe and acquire data on how the riflescope behaves during recoil. For this, the data acquisition and test setup should be easy to maintain, portable, and fast setup addition, measurements should be repeatable and low-cost. A literature review was conducted to check what has been done, what sensors and data acquisition controllers were used, the setup type, and the results. The sensor selection process required numerous specifications to filter the possible sensors for the ideal selection. The main factors and basis for the appointment were weight, G force, frequency, and price. The calculated theoretical max acceleration suffered by the rifle setup is 114g. The sensor also must be easily mounted/unmounted to/from the riflescope body. Furthermore, the sensor should be rigidly fixed not to suffer any unnecessary vibration from the interface and interfere with the measured data. Finally, the data acquisition should be accomplished relatively quickly to measure all the necessary data points. Sensors and accessories from various manufacturers were researched that fit the requirements. However, due to cost limitations, the selected sensor was the ADXL372. The testing setup includes a rifle and riflescope assembly on a stand. The sensor is guided and fixed on the riflescope, and a microcontroller reads and stores the acquired values. As a result, the testing setup is easy to transport and has a quick and repeatable structure. The measured acceleration values can calculate acceleration curves, displacement, velocity, and forces. The setup is ideal as it can be used to monitor the riflescope reaction on each test point, and results can have many uses, such as validating a numerical model FEA simulation. This paper will present and discuss the instrumentation and setup needed to read acceleration values on a riflescope from the firearm recoil and analyze the data for further use and interpretation.

Keywords: Rifle scope, Recoil, accelerometer, MEMS, ICP, Arduino, ADXL372.

COMFORT ANALYSIS COMPARISON BETWEEN ALFAPENDULAR AND INTERCITY PORTUGUESE TRAINS AT THE NORTH RAIL

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, trains are one of the most used public transportation modes. Comfort is the key to keeping and attracting new users. Vibration highly influences comfort levels and, once it is derived from the train motion it is stated as a primary concern. Due to contact with the seat and floor, passengers are subjected to whole-body vibration. ISO 2631 standard is fully dedicated to the evaluation of this type of vibration. Following its approach, the present research evaluates the comfort levels of Alfabendular and Intercity trains operating in Portugal at the Porto Campanhã – Lisbon Oriente connection. Measurements were performed at the beginning, middle, and end of the train, allowing a comparison between seat types within the same train and the same types from different trains. Results showed higher comfort levels for the Alfabendular trains, while for the Intercity train, both middle and end of train locations were ranked as “Little uncomfortable”. As a complementary analysis, it was observed the vibration transmission of the seat based on the Seat Effective Amplitude Transmissibility (SEAT). Results were above 100%, showing vibration amplification by all tested seats. Higher SEAT values were found for the Intercity train seat. This was the first study conducted on Portuguese trains regarding comfort analysis and vibration transmission.

Keywords: Railways, Whole-body vibration, Vibration transmission, SEAT.

HAND EXOSKELETON FOR REHABILITATION AND FUNCTIONALIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Many diseases and injuries of the hand require rehabilitation to restore function. However, the high human, financial, spatial, and temporal costs associated with rehabilitation often mean that the population in need does not have access to optimal rehabilitative care. Therefore, devices that complement the therapist are a possible solution, as they make rehabilitation more independent and frequent, and save healthcare facilities the aforementioned resources. Nevertheless, these devices are not widely distributed in the market, mainly due to their poor accessibility. The newly designed exoskeleton has four motors and a redundant transmission system that allows independent flexion and extension of each finger, except the thumb. Kinematics were analyzed with motion studies and loads were evaluated with static studies and structural analysis using motion loads. In the simulations, both flexion and extension were achieved in four seconds. A prototype transmission system was built and its kinematics matched that of the simulation and corresponded to the biomechanics of the fingers. At maximum flexion, the exoskeleton would be able to hold small objects and exert a normal force of up to 20 N with structural integrity.

Keywords: Engineering design, exoskeleton, hand rehabilitation, hand functionalization.

SPARSE REPRESENTATION IN THE RECONSTRUCTION OF ULTRA-HIGH-RESOLUTION PET IMAGES

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ABSTRACT

Reconstructed pictures in positron emission tomography (PET) research are frequently noisy and low quality. The low-count issue is the main source of these issues. Sparse prediction is more likely to be chosen as the solution as sparse technology is employed more frequently. I suggest a brand-new sparse prior technique in this research to process low quality PET reconstructed pictures. Two dictionaries (D1 for low-resolution PET images and D2 for high-resolution PET images) are trained from plenty of actual PET image patches in the proposed approach. The sparse representation for each patch of the input PET picture is then obtained using D1. Finally, D2 is used to create a high-resolution PET image from this sparse representation. The results of the studies show that the suggested strategy has superior effects that improve image resolution and detail recovery that are stable. In terms of root mean square error, this technique performs better quantitatively than older methods (RMSE). The suggested method offers a fresh and effective way to enhance the image quality of PET reconstructions. The back projection technique was created for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) picture reconstruction of under sampled data and has been used to denoise dynamic PET images.

Keywords: PET imaging, data acquisition, artifacts, resolution, information technologies.

THE METHOD OF DETECTION OF SIGNALS USING DIFFERENTIAL TRANSFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

In practice, to obtain confidential information from the original source, various types of devices, so-called embedded devices, are used. The most widely used in the practice of industrial intelligence are devices with a radio channel for the transmission of intercepted information, so-called radio jamming devices. These devices use the energy of electromagnetic waves to transmit information, which does not affect human senses and can spread over considerable distances, overcoming natural and artificial obstacles. Thanks to these properties, it is possible to observe the object from almost any remote point secretly. Therefore, the detection of embedded device signals is a very urgent scientific task. This report is dedicated to solving this problem.

A method of detecting random signals emitted by hidden transmitters is proposed. The process is based on a mathematical model of differential signal transformations within the framework of correlation theory. It is proven that this approach to determining the correlation function of a random signal is justified. It is shown that the random signal of hidden transmitters consists of the sum of all discrete components of the differential spectrum for the correlation function. Which allows you to get the parameters of the signal by which it can be distinguished from other random signals of the tested radio range. The simulation was carried out and the random signal's numerical parameters and graphic materials were obtained: expectations and deviations. The obtained modeling materials visually proved the efficiency of the proposed method.

Keywords: random signal, discrete components, spectrum, model, mathematical expectations.

IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR EVALUATING THE CARRIER FREQUENCY OF THE SIGNAL DURING DATA TRANSMISSION IN TELECOMMUNICATION CONTROL AND DISTANCE LEARNING SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Effectiveness of the application of telecommunications systems is directly influenced by the effectiveness of the functioning of each component and device of its design.

The article directly examines the issue of improving the carrier frequency estimation methodology for data transmission in telecommunication management and distance learning systems. The essence of the solution lies in proposals for improving the efficiency of frequency estimation at the input signal synchronization stage, which is presented on the example of a satellite telecommunication control system and distance learning. Namely, the analysis of modern satellite telecommunications systems was carried out and the features that affect the effectiveness of carrier frequency estimation and input signal synchronization were determined. The main inconsistencies are the low energy of the input signal receiving channel, significant signal frequency uncertainty, and the presence of "neighboring channels" receiving the input signal. It was determined that satellite communication systems during data transmission work in the mode with multi-station access in the variant of operation with frequency division of channels, which can receive data packets in the mode of multiple access or when providing a data reception channel on demand. At the same time, the operation of telecommunications systems can proceed both in continuous and in batch modes of receiving the input signal. It is taken into account that coherent processing of the input signal is carried out in demodulators of satellite telecommunications and interference-resistant coding is used. To solve the task of estimating the carrier frequency of the input signal in coherent demodulators of modern satellite telecommunications, taking into account the above-defined inconsistencies and features, the article proposes a methodical approach. The essence of this approach is to determine the potential boundary of variances of the obtained estimates of the carrier frequency and to develop algorithms for estimating the carrier frequency of the input signal separately for continuous and batch modes of input data transmission based on the fast Fourier transform.

Keywords: Frequency, signal, uncertainty, carrier, estimation.

THE PERSPECTIVES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLECT IN SERVICE OF PHARMACY, MEDICINE, AND PUBLIC HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

Aim of The Research was to study and analyze the perspectives of artificial intellect in service of pharmacy, medicine and public health. Digital health is largely shaped by experts outside of the health sector and this provides an opportunity for interdisciplinary collaboration to develop the foundation of digital health education. Education in pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences must be needs-based to meet the current and changing demands of digital health. These requirements should reflect the needs of all members in all sectors and career levels in pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences, from clinical pharmacist to drug research. Digital medicine-The digital drug system currently contains four main components: an inert sensor embedded in an inert tablet, a non-medicated sensor (patch) worn by the patient, a mobile application and a web-based dashboard. Upon interaction with gastric fluids, the ingestible sensor is activated and connects to a wearable sensor that sends a signal to a mobile device where it can be viewed by patients or subsequently viewed by healthcare providers and caregivers using secure mobile-based and cloud-based applications. based software. It also has the ability to record other behavioral and physiological parameters, such as physical activity, heart rate, skin temperature, sleep and digital therapeutics. Aspiring pharmacists, pharmaceutical scientists and healthcare professionals. Students are most involved in the era of digital transformation. Their participation in digital health education processes is an important opportunity as they support the adoption and promotion of these digital health technologies. Several studies have been conducted to understand digital health skills, knowledge and competencies among pharmacy students. Since most of the research conducted is done in countries such as the US, UK and Australia, the global state of digital health in pharmacy schools is not fully understood. The vast amount of health data provides the opportunity to use more artificial intellect and machine learning in the practice of pharmacy to solve important issues related to medication management and use. Trend analysis in large data sets can reveal individual patient risk of adverse events, behavioral aspects, compliance profiles, etc. A pharmacist is a professional expert who can augment a data scientist's expertise to create services. Understanding the terminology and concepts used in artificial intellect will help pharmacists engage constructively with data scientists and collaborate with them to develop models that enhance patient care. Digital health systems can also empower and engage patients, making them co-designers of care. Shared decision-making between healthcare workers and patients requires trust, a sense of partnership and transparency in their interactions.

Keywords: Perspectives, artificial intellect, service, pharmacy, medicine, public health.

DEVELOPMENT OF A SYSTEM OF MONITORING AND CONTROL OF PROCESSES OF THERMOCHEMICAL OIL TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to improving the quality of systems for monitoring and controlling the processes of destruction of armored shells, coalescence and dynamic settling of emulsified

water droplets. It is noted that the determining parameters of control and management are: dosage, temperature of the processes of dehydration and desalting of oil, the level of the water cushion and the pressure in the settling apparatus. As a result of the research, it was found that in order to improve the quality of control and management of oil preparation processes, it is necessary to take into account the influence of the oscillatory movement of the oil emulsion in settling apparatus, depending on changes in a number of parameters. The work of the developed system for monitoring and controlling the processes of oil preparation consists in the uneven distribution of the flow of oil emulsion between the settling devices operating in parallel with the impact on the actuators installed in the flows in front of each of them. The conducted studies have shown that the dispersed composition is the only integral indicator of the state of the OE, since the change in the values of flow factors, such as the rate of destruction of the armor shells, coalescence and crushing of emulsified water droplets, is ultimately reflected in it.

Keywords: oil, surfactants, dosing process, emulsified water droplets, technological model, decision support.

LOARA BASED TRACKING SYSTEM FOR ELDERLY

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ABSTRACT

People are having a lot of trouble due to the loss of people and other living things they take care of and responsibilities; If the person we are responsible for is lucky, there is the fact that it can only result in stress, fear and disorientation, but sometimes even a disaster. In recent years, due to the disappearance and the increasing unpleasant events that are the result of these events, We have developed a system named "Akdenizde Kal" in the project in order to prevent these and similar situations. The system uses accessory which transfers the Gps location via Lora modulation and Radio Waves for people and other persons who are not able to use the system. Gateway that transfers this information to the internet using IoT (Internet of Things) technology and transfers it to the people responsible for the follow- We have developed an Android app that gives early warning before its status.

Keywords: Lora, IoT, Gateway, Android.

A NEW EFFECTIVE METHOD FOR 2D IMAGE CONSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

In this work a new method which is convenient to release the numerical solutions for two dimensional image construction problem connected with cylindrical bodies buried in a non-magnetic and non-conductive simple half space is established. The mentioned method is based on the determination of the object function with the use of spectral expansion technique

and method of moment for the horizontal and vertical coordinates, respectively. The particular structure for the corresponding spectral expansion is obtained by the consideration of the basis functions such that the classical well-known ill-posedness effect of an inverse problem is reduced to a minimum. The unknown coefficients β_{ij} which involve in this spectral expansion are also determined by using the Fourier transform of the diffracted field with respect to y_1 such as

$$\hat{u}_D(\alpha, y_2) = k_1^2 \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=-N}^N \beta_{ij} \hat{\psi}_j(\alpha) \int_{y_2^{(i)-h}}^{y_2^{(i)+h}} \hat{G}(\alpha, y_2, 0, y_2') dy_2'. \quad (1)$$

In (1) \hat{G} is the Fourier transform of the Green's function related to the two part space and $\hat{\psi}_j(\alpha)$ is the Fourier transform of the basis function given by

$$\psi_j(y_1) = \begin{cases} \cos\left(\frac{\pi(y_1 - j\ell)}{2\ell}\right), & |y_1 - j\ell| \leq \ell \\ 0, & |y_1 - j\ell| \geq \ell \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The object function w mentioned above can be given for each layer by

$$w(y_1, y_2^{(i)}) = \frac{\sum_{j=-N}^N \beta_{ij} \psi_j(y_1)}{u_0(y_1, y_2^{(i)}) + u_D(y_1, y_2^{(i)})}, \quad i = 1, \dots, M \quad (3)$$

where u_0 and u_D are the incident and diffracted field in the body, respectively.

In order to check the applicability and as well as the accuracy of the method developed in this study some illustrative examples are also presented.

A RELATIVISTIC STUDY OF A MOVING LINE SOURCE RADIATION

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to reveal the exact relativistic expressions of the electromagnetic fields radiated by a uniformly moving time harmonic line source having a finite length ℓ . As it is well known, the knowledge of these fields that can be defined as those of created by moving antennas plays a crucial role in the applications related to telecommunication engineering. To solve the problem mentioned above one considers the corresponding source S is located being parallel to the $O'z'$ -axis of a frame denoted by K' which moves with a constant rectilinear velocity v in the direction of Ox -axis of the observation frame K (see Fig.1.). If the frequency and the amplitude of the current related to the line source S are denoted by ω' and I , respectively, then the current and charge densities observed in K' become

$$\vec{J}' = I \cos(\omega't') \delta(x' - a) \delta(y' - b) [U(z' + \ell/2) - U(z' - \ell/2)] \vec{e}_z \quad (1.a)$$

and

$$\rho' = -(I/\omega') \sin(\omega't') \delta(x' - a) \delta(y' - b) [\delta(z' + \ell/2) - \delta(z' - \ell/2)]. \quad (1.b)$$

In (1.a,b) \vec{e}_z being unit vector of $O'z'$ -axis, $U(\cdot)$ and $\delta(\cdot)$ stand for Heaviside unit and Dirac delta functions. It is also worthwhile to notice that t' appearing in these expressions shows the time measured in the frame K .

Fig.1. A source moving with velocity $\mathbf{v} = v \mathbf{e}_x$

By considering the well known Lorentz transformation [1] and the source transformation formulas [2]

the densities of the source observed in K are obtained as to be

$$\rho = -(I\gamma / \omega) \sin(\omega t - \omega v x / c^2) \delta(x - vt - a / \gamma) \delta(y - b) [\delta(z + \ell / 2) - \delta(z - \ell / 2)]. \quad (2.a)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \vec{J} = (I / \gamma) \cos(\omega t - \omega v x / c^2) \delta(x - vt - a / \gamma) \delta(y - b) [U(z + \ell / 2) - U(z - \ell / 2)] \vec{e}_z + \rho v \vec{e}_x$$

(2.b)

where $\gamma = (1 - v^2 / c^2)^{-1/2}$ and $\omega = \gamma \omega'$. Consequently, with the use of delayed vector potential

$\vec{A}(x, y, z, t)$ and scalar potential $V(x, y, z, t)$ which are computed for the source distributions given in (2.a,b), the expressions of the electromagnetic fields radiated by the moving line source mentioned here can easily be presented in the frame K .

CNN-BASED VISUAL INSPECTION OF ELECTRONIC CARD ASSEMBLIES FOR DEFECT DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

Industrial solutions for visual inspection of printed circuit boards (PCBs) have been improved in recent decades to become part of the standard quality control in the manufacturing process (led by China today). However, most of the methods used to detect defects in PCBs result ineffective for defect detection in electronic cards assemblies whose components have been manually placed and soldered, causing a high rate of false positives due to the high variation in card finishing. In this article, we present a methodology to implement an automatic defect detection system for manually soldered PCB assemblies. The proposed system consists of 3 subsystems: image processing to highlight defects and features, automatic selection of components ROIs to be analyzed and a classifier based on a deep neural network classifier trained under a specific catalog of defects to be searched for. Details for the construction of a defect catalog and coding of the training database for the ANN training are presented. In order to validate methodology, an experimental platform with partially controlled lighting was built. ANN was trained with a database of images of real electronic cards with the aforementioned characteristics. Experimental results showed a reduction of false positives with respect to a commercial system and the correct detection of faults.

Keywords: CNN, Quality Control, Image Descriptor, AI.

NUMERICALLY STABLE ELECTROMAGNETIC WAVE SCATTERING ALGORITHMS FOR AN ARRAY OF LOSSY DIELECTRIC CYLINDERS OF ARBITRARY CROSS-SECTION

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ABSTRACT

Integral equations play key role in establishing the time-harmonic electromagnetic wave scattering by cylindrical objects. When the semi-transparent obstacles like lossy dielectrics are under consideration, the corresponding integral representation of the scattered field exploit free space Green's function of Helmholtz equation written in the region that the scattered field is non-zero where this field is zero in the other region creating two different formulations. Former leads to the boundary integral equations while the latter leads to null-field integral equations [1]. The equivalent surface current densities on the boundary separating lossy dielectric from its host are sought for with Galerkin type weighted residual methods during the former while eigenfunction expansions are utilized for the latter [2]. Both lead us to a linear algebraic equation system that is ill-conditioned in general. That means their truncated solutions in computer is sensitive to small perturbations of the source of the equation. This leads to numerical catastrophe for increasing truncation numbers of these linear algebraic equations [3]. To ensure the numerical stability of these systems a regularization procedure to well-condition them is critically important. For example, the Analytical Regularization Method approaches these integral equations to reach a linear algebraic system, truncation of which only improves the accuracy of the corresponding solution as the system dimension increases [4-6]. The mentioned status of the conditioning gets more important when we analyze the scattering by not single but a multitude of such objects as an array of lossy dielectric cylinders of arbitrary cross-section. Because the iterative solvers engaged in numerical realizations perform within a strong dependence on the condition of the linear algebraic system.

The corresponding boundary integral equations will be discretized by a super-algebraically converging algorithm [2,4,5], while the null-field method will be regularized via proper scaling of the unknowns eliminating their fast increasing and decreasing factors [6]. The numerical implementation essentials of both integral equation types mentioned above for the mentioned type of the problem that occurs in many practical applications like photonic crystals, meta-materials, array sensors, gratings are the main course of the presentation.

Keywords: Integral equations, cylindrical scatterers, Analytical Regularization Method.

BIOMIMETIC, COCKROACH-SHAPED, MICRO ROBOTIC SPY BUG

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ABSTRACT

Typically, a spy bug or listening device comprises of a transmitter and a microphone receiver. The receiver microphone may record voiceovers and au- dio. Listening and recording the

conversations around are the essential purposes of the spy bug. Listening gadgets pose a number of concerns. It becomes difficult to place the bug in the room of the person being listened to or when the targets of the bug are aware that they are being listened to, it will be relatively simple for them to locate it. In order to avoid such situations, we designed our listening device to be 2 to 3 cm long and to resemble the *Blatta orientalis* members, which are common all over the world. This bioinspired micro robotic device can be able to find its own way and reach its desired destination by walking. Even if its position is identified, it will not be recognized that it is an electrical device due to its insect look. It will migrate at night, like other cockroaches in nature and this regular displacement action will make it even more difficult to locate the device.

Keywords: Biomimetic; Micro robotics; Bug.

CALCULATION OF EVS ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT AND VALIDATION WITH PHYSICAL TEST

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, due to the limited fuel resources for the increasing energy demand, the search for alternative energy sources in transportation and in many different sectors continues rapidly. Due to carbon dioxide emission and its effect on global warming, it is aimed to limit the use of fuel in the future and to use electrical energy, which is cleaner energy, widely. In this study, mathematical modeling of an electric minibus used in urban transportation in daily life was made in MATLAB/Simulink environment. The technical and dynamic features of the vehicle were used in the modeling. According to the UITP Project E-Sort procedure, Standardized On-Road Test Cycles-1 (Sort-1), Sort-2 and Sort-3 road conditions were applied to the vehicle modeled in the simulation environment. Energy consumption and maximum distance rates that the vehicle can travel with a full charge were calculated in 3 different road conditions. As a result of the study, thanks to the data obtained from the simulation environment it is aimed to obtain an approximate maximum range data that the vehicle can get while it is in the design phase before the physical test, with less cost. Studies on mathematical modeling and development of electrical vehicles (EVs), the use of which are rapidly becoming widespread, have been increasing. While the vehicles to be produced reach the design stage, their components are selected according to the results of mathematical calculations. In addition, the design is completed according to the data obtained in the simulation. Within the scope of Vehicle Dynamics Tests, Energy Consumption Test of the prototype vehicle produced is carried out. With this test, the vehicle's energy consumption and maximum distance are measured. Component changes made according to physical test results in prototype vehicles cause losses in terms of time and cost. With this study, it is aimed to compare the simulation results with the physical test results. Then, with the data obtained from the comparison results, it is aimed to perform the maximum distance and energy consumption test in the simulation environment before the prototype vehicle is produced, thus minimizing the loss of time and cost.

In this study, a mathematical model of an electric minibus used in urban transportation was created according to its dynamic characteristics and energy consumption was calculated in simulation. MATLAB Simulink is used in the scope of this study. Additional to simulation study

and mathematical modelling, physical tests are also performed to compare simulated results. According to the UITP PROJECT E-SORT procedure, the prototype vehicle was instrumented with the data logger, GPS, V-Box devices connected to the Can communication path of the vehicle and the energy consumption amount is observed. Within the scope of this study, it is aimed to compare the simulation results with the data obtained as a result of the test. As a result of the study, the accuracy of the results obtained in the simulation with physical tests, the margin of error and the deviations in maximum distance calculations evaluated.

Keywords: Electric Vehicle, Energy Consumption Calculation, Mathematical modeling, Physical Energy Consumption.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE APPLICATIONS IN AQUACULTURE SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

The use of intelligent production systems in the aquaculture sector has been increasing rapidly, especially in recent years. These include studies such as identification of fish species, monitoring of water quality parameters in shrimp farms, diagnosis of diseases seen in fish farms using image analysis techniques. In addition, water quality parameters can be monitored instantly with the Internet of Things method and the daily operations of the farms are organized by using these data. On the other hand, changes in environmental parameters in aquaculture facilities may cause problems that directly affect production. Diseases encountered in aquaculture facilities can be given as an example. The loss of the aquaculture sector in the world due to diseases reaches billion dollars. Artificial intelligence applications predict the emergence periods of diseases in advance and provide data to the producer to save time to take the necessary measures and thus prevent losses. The study shows promising positive results in this direction.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning Techniques, Internet of Things, Aquaculture.

FROM THE INTERNET OF FARM TO THE INTERNET OF AQUACULTURE

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ABSTRACT

Today, the Internet of Things (IoT) concept has come to the forefront. IoT represents an intelligent network of devices that connect and share data with each other using various communication protocols. The equivalent and applications of IoT technology in agriculture are known as the "Internet of Farm (IoF)". IoF applications promise to increase agricultural product and food production by increasing product quality and product efficiency, reducing unnecessary chemical use, preventing environmental pollution, protecting resources, and controlling costs. Thanks to IoF technology, businesses can analyze their products and resources, evaluate their

real-time production performance and plan for the future to use their resources more effectively. In addition, the widespread use of IoT enables agriculture to achieve higher yields at lower input costs, reducing environmental pollution and labor costs.

Within the scope of the planned study, it is aimed to design and manufacture an example of an economic benefit-oriented, lean industrial design condition monitoring station that will allow instant monitoring of environmental parameters, feeding protocol, and fish produced in fish farming and inference analysis related to aquaculture from these data. By evaluating the data obtained through the stations, efficient feeding programs can be created. In addition, the prediction of changes or threats that may occur in the cultural environment will enable measures to be taken in advance and thus losses can be prevented. In addition, the quality of the product to be obtained at the end of the season and the amount of harvest can be estimated, thus enabling the producer to make more accurate economic planning. Since the stations measure the physicochemical parameters of water, they can also serve as local stations for the areas where they are located. Data and evaluation results will be accessible via web and mobile device applications with a subscription system. This study also constitutes an infrastructure for an early warning system (fish species-specific disease warnings, active substance recommendations, and development of a spraying program project), which is also planned to be carried out in the future.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Internet of Farm, Smart Agriculture, Condition Monitoring System, Internet of Aquaculture.

DETECTION OF PASSENGER DENSITY AT BUS STOPS WITH DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Today, the increase in the use of public transportation in cities causes some problems. One of these problems is that the buses do not arrive at the stops on time. This means a loss of time and money for both passengers and bus operators. Real-time monitoring systems that detect the density at bus stops can be used to solve this problem. In recent years, it has been observed that convolutional neural network (CNN) based models have been preferred more than machine learning based applications in studies for object detection applications. In this study, Deep Learning based software was developed to detect passenger density at bus stops. In the study, open source dataset ShanghaiTech Part-A and ShanghaiTech Part-B were used. The dataset was trained with Yolov3, Sparse R-CNN, Faster R-CNN and YoloF architectures. Experiments were performed with 100 and 200 epochs, and the highest mAP(s) value was obtained with the 50.6% Faster R-CNN model. At the end of the study, real-time passenger detection software was developed.

Keywords: Deep learning, passenger detection, object detection.

LORA BASED TRACKING SYSTEM FOR ELDERLY

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ABSTRACT

People are having a lot of trouble due to the loss of people and other living things they take care of and responsibilities; If the person we are responsible for is lucky, there is the fact that it can only result in stress, fear, and disorientation, but sometimes even a disaster. In recent years, due to the disappearance and the increasingly unpleasant events that are the result of these events, We have developed a system named "Akdenizde Kal" in the project in order to prevent these and similar situations. The system uses an accessory that transfers the Gps location via Lora modulation and Radio Waves for people and other persons who are not able to use the system. A gateway that transfers this information to the internet using IoT (Internet of Things) technology and transfers it to the people responsible for the following- We have developed an Android app that gives early warning before its status.

Keywords: Lora, IoT, Elderly, Mobil Application.

COMPARING DIFFERENT MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR DISEASE PREDICTION

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning algorithms are one of the most used methods in forecasting. Predicting a disease or a medical condition using collected health data is a wide area of application for these methods. Discussed study aims at making a comparison among different algorithms of supervised machine learning, performance metrics and efficiency of usage for heart disease risk forecasting. Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), Machine Learning algorithms like k-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Random Forest (RF), Neural Network (NN) and dataset about heart disease were chosen to verify the validity of methods. Heart disease has been one of the major issues in medicine for a long time. Many people of all ages around the world are suffering from this disease. The goal is to recognize Heart disease among various patients and take measures before the disease gets worse or becomes too late to treat. A machine learning system can decrease the number of such cases by predicting the disease. This paper displays the findings and analysis of identifying Heart disease using Machine Learning algorithms.

Keywords: Forecasting, Machine Learning in Forecasting, algorithms, Neural Networks, Heart Disease, Machine Learning, predict, dataset, RF, LR, NN, KNN, DT, SVM.

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